

The INCLUDING RN/TEC gaps

**The G516 gap:
Lack of small (capable of low flying) UAVs with payload high
enough to carry out radiation measurements**

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Executive summary

This document provides an extensive overview of the state of the art in research, development and use of low-flying UAVs in radiological and nuclear emergencies. The main driver behind this study is the G516 gap listed in the dynamic catalogue of the ENCIRCLE project but it is also referenced to the IFAFRI capability gaps. After an overview of possible intervention scenarios where low flying UAVs can improve the detection, identification and monitoring capabilities of First Responders, the document critically revises the current achievements in integrating radiation system measurements on UAVs. In particular the study considers some explicative examples of results from R&D projects/activities and more advanced solutions already mature for a commercial exploitation. Critical for the entire study is the reference to the EU Regulations 2019/947 and 2019/945 that set out the framework for the safe operation of civil drones in the European skies. The document also overviews actual barrier for further penetration of the technology in the security market and standardization issues. Finally, it describes lessons learnt during INCLUDING project exercise and training activities where UAVs with radiation measurements device onboard were deployed in simulations close to real operational scenarios. With new solutions and advances progressing at rapid pace, the document is intended as a snapshot taken at the moment of its release but that will be updated in due course during INCLUDING project execution.

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1. Introduction

1.1. The INCLUDING project and ENCIRCLE

Within the framework of developing a Federation of cooperating members, the INCLUDING project focuses on enhancing practically applicable know-how for practitioners in the Radiological (R) and Nuclear (N) Safety and Security sectors. This includes, inter alia, evaluating the use of innovative technology and procedures, such as Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs; drones). In doing this, INCLUDING intends also to deepen specific gaps that have been recognized as relevant by practitioners for an effective uptake of the technology. To this aim, INCLUDING has taken as reference the ENCIRCLE¹ dynamic catalogue containing a comprehensive list of CBRNe gaps collated from other EU and international projects. These gaps are organized with a codename and grouped, according to the appropriate operational functions identified in the PRACTICE² project and named with a proper taxonomy. In particular the *ENCIRCLE Gap 516* identifies the need for *UAVs capable of low flying with payload high enough to carry out radiation measurements*. INCLUDING, within the planned activities of its Work Package 3 devoted to *Training gaps analysis and scenarios development*, intends to contribute to further explore the GAP 516 by analyzing the requirements of First Responders (FRs) in this topic area and conducting an international analysis of the Commercial-off-the-Shelf (COTS) UAV and radiation detector market in order to identify practically applicable solutions.

1.2. Purpose of the document

The objective of this INCLUDING study is to address the ENCIRCLE G516 gap, entitled *Lack of small (capable of low flying) UAVs with payload high enough to carry out radiation measurements*.

As will be detailed in Sec.4.5, in this context for *small UAVs capable of low flying* it is intended the **A2 and A3 subcategories of Open drones' category with Maximum Take-Off Mass (MTOM) in the range 900g-25 kg and as defined in the EU Regulations 2019/947 and 2019/945³**.

For instance, drones like the Yamaha RG1 (MTOM 95Kg) are considered outside the perimeter of this study, , although it has been used with e LaBr3:Ce scintillation detectors to measure ground contamination in an area of 5Km of radius around the Fukushima Daichi Power plant in 2015⁴.

The study is oriented towards identifying the requirements of First Responders (FRs) in civil crisis scenarios and does not detail technical aspects of the multiple UAV applications in the defense sector. Nevertheless, it contains an example of civil/military cooperation. With many organizations seeking ways to evaluate the potential for new operational applications integrating UAVs technologies into existing physical security system operations and RN

¹ <http://encircle-cbrn.eu>

² <https://practice-fp7-security.eu>

³ <https://www.easa.europa.eu/document-library/easy-access-rules/easy-access-rules-unmanned-aircraft-systems-regulation-eu>

⁴ Y. Sanada, T. Torii Aerial radiation monitoring around the Fukushima Dai-ichi nuclear power plant using an unmanned helicopter, *Journal of Environmental Radioactivity* 139 (2015) 294e299

emergency response plans, the document intends to contribute to raise a more structured knowledge on this multidisciplinary and rapidly evolving matter.

The document reflects the current state of the art at the moment of its release and incorporates also lessons learnt during INCLUDING Joint Actions so far executed, as well as outcomes from discussions in project workshops.

A relevant question is: to whom this document is of interest? The answer is rooted in the document structure. It can be of use to a wide range of stakeholders, from readers with no technical expertise in radiation measurements, to those with very basic knowledge of UAVs technology, from First Responders with an interest in innovation in their response capabilities to RN crisis managers, from technology developers from R&D institutes and commercial organizations to university and master courses students. In fact, the document is at some extent modular, in the sense that each reader may move directly to the section of its own interest and identify the appropriate pieces of information and knowledge.

Finally, the document describes developments in the sector with reference to some R&D and commercial activities. The criteria for the selection of these examples are purely grounded on scientific interests and do not have any ambition to be exhaustive, also in light of the continuous release of innovations worldwide.

1.3. Glossary of Acronyms

Acronym	Description
AGL	Above ground level
AMSL	Above mean sea level
BVLOS	Beyond Visual line of sight
CPS	Counts per second
FPV	First-Person- View
FR	First responder
FWHM	Full width at half maximum
GAEC	Greek Atomic Energy Commission
GM	Geiger-Mueller
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSC	Ground control system
HD	High definition
IR	Infrared
MPS	Mission Planning System
MTOM	Maximum Take Off Mass
N	Nuclear
R	Radiological
RIASTM	Remote Isotopic Analysis System ™

RMD	Radiation measurement device
SUAS	Small UAV system
UAV	Unmanned aerial vehicle
URD	UAV-Radiation Detection
VIS	Video/photo images
VLOS	Visual line of sight
VTOL	Vertical takeoff and landing

2. The G516 gap and its relevance in INCLUDING

The ENCIRCLE database lists multiple gaps with a focus on the CBRN domain. *ENCIRCLE Gap 516* identifies the need for a *UAV capable of low flying with a payload high enough to carry out radiation measurements*. These requirements reflect the INCLUDING scenario, where First Responders (FR) are tasked to carry out an aerial radiation survey in an area contaminated or supposed to be contaminated by an accident or by a deliberated criminal action.

The basic scenario assumes that FRs are called to a prompt and cost-effective deployment of unmanned aerial vehicles equipped with sensors for visual inspection and radiological survey in hard-to-reach, hazardous, or dangerous environments and with the primary aim to reduce worker doses and improve worker safety during the operations. The use of **subcategories A2 and A3 of Open drones' category** (see Sec. 4.5) can offer an interesting and viable solution (i.e., easily deployable) for the detection of radiation in the considered scenarios.

Whilst there are multiple COTS small UAVs worldwide, either these drones are a priori unsuited for carrying the weight of a radiation measurement device, or their operational flight time is severely limited due to the payload, thereby making them unsuitable for such operations. In other words, such a Small UAV-Radiation Detection (URD) System reflects a compromise between minimizing the weight for the radiation detector in order to achieve maximum drone flight time.

The Gap 516 assumes particular relevance in some specific nuclear safety and security scenarios as listed in Sec.4.3.5. If from one side the safety related scenarios are almost well known and with real cases to be taken as reference, on the other side new nuclear security scenarios continue to evolve and fewer cases are available for assessing lessons learnt. This implies a natural link between the present study and the activity of Task3.1 of INCLUDING that is devoted to the study of the evolution of nuclear security scenarios. In this regard, it is prominent to consider the present study in INCLUDING as a contribution to promote the adoption of *UAV capable of low flying with payload high enough to carry out radiation measurements* as key assets in the IAEA provision to the Member States to develop a proper Nuclear Security Detection Architecture (NSDA)⁵. In fact, UAV capable of low flying and equipped with radiation sensors may be deployed to perform the search for concealed radioactive sources as a result of an information alert. In this case it is required that a radiation detection system operating on the UAV and with high sensitivity can compensate for the radiation absorption due to shielding material. The low flying capability is required because

⁵ https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/Pub1613_web.pdf

the detector intercepted radiation can be modelled as $1/z^2$ functional decay, where z is the UAV flight height, and hence any aerial mapping is highly sensitive to the altitude at which the measurements are taken.

In view of these considerations, recent years have seen an increasing interest and multiple efforts to address a solution for the Gap 516, both within research projects and in commercial development programs of SMEs and industries. The state of the art (SOTA) is in continuous evolution and INCLUDING, during the project timeframe, will be steadily assessing the progresses and with the aim to promote and execute exercises with real radiation sources in the project's testbeds.

In fact, apart from the specific technical aspects that will be detailed in the document, at present one of the main priorities related to Gap 516, seems to be the testing of research and commercial products in operative scenarios simulated as closely as possible to real life conditions. This is key to ascertain the real added value of this emerging technology for FRs and crisis managers, to identify issues related to the integration of the technology in prevention/response plans, and to deliver feedbacks to technology developers for further improvements. Most of the time, regulatory and budgetary constraints of research and commercial activities limit the testing to drills, where UAVs with radiation measurement capabilities are deployed as stand-alone solutions in isolated areas, not fully representative of the real RN emergencies settings. The INCLUDING Joint Actions (see Sec. 7) are specifically designed to bridge this gap.

3. Relevance to the IFAFRI Capability Gaps

The *International Forum to Advance First Responder Innovation*⁶(IFAFRI) focuses on enhancing and expanding the development of affordable technology and innovative solutions to improve first responder safety, efficiency and effectiveness. IFAFRI integrates organizations from fourteen States and DG-DEVCO of the European Commission.

IFAFRI has identified ten areas where new or improved technologies could greatly enhance the safety, effectiveness and efficiency of first responders. The Gap516 of the ENCIRCLE Dynamic Catalogue is directly linked to the following IFAFRI Capability Gaps:

- Capability Gap 6 - The ability to obtain critical information remotely about the extent, perimeter, or interior of the incident

A detailed analysis of the IFAFRI capability gaps 6 can be found at the IFAFRI website⁷ and it encompasses:

- A Statement of Objectives (SOO) to provide a technical overview of the global first responder needs and direct researchers who may be interested in pursuing the development of a solution;
- A “deep dive” analysis document to further define and segment the relevant markets for the capability gap.

⁶ https://www.internationalresponderforum.org/about_ifafri

⁷ <https://www.internationalresponderforum.org/>

SSO of IFAFRI gap 6 reports that emergencies of many types pose problems for responders in obtaining situational awareness of what is occurring in and around the incident scene. Current capability to conduct surveillance is generally reliant on airborne assets (primarily helicopters or airplanes) that may be limited by conditions in their ability to approach the incident scene. In RN scenarios, UAV capable of flying low are game changing assets to address this gap but if and only if they can accommodate as payload detectors capable of recording accurately radiation levels. Based on the SSO of IFAFRI gap 6, in this document are further developed the specific needs of FR that UAV capable of low flying can satisfy (Sec.4.1), the mission scenarios (Sec. 4.2), UAV and radiation detectors requirements (Sec. 4.3 and Sec4.4). Specific market analysis carried out in Sec.4.5, 4.6 4.7 and Sec.5 are aimed at specifying for *UAV capable of low flying with payload high enough to carry out radiation measurements* the results reported in the IFAFRI Gap 6 “deep dive” document.

4. Technical Section

4.1. Global concept of operations (CONOPS)

In developing CONPOS for the use of UAV in nuclear and radiological emergencies, it is necessary to start with a clear definition of what a RN emergency is. According to IAEA⁸ a RN emergency is a situation in which there is, or is perceived to be, a hazard due to:

- The energy resulting from a nuclear chain reaction or from the decay of the products of a chain reaction;
- Radiation exposure, where the term radiation refers only to ionizing radiation

It is clear from the definition above that nuclear and radiological emergencies can occur in a variety of forms and degrees of severity and magnitude. A commensurate response to the emergency encompasses the deployment of technologies qualified to operate in the mixed intervention environments and most notably with radiation detectors capable to generate actionable data. In this context, it is worth noticing that illicit trafficking of nuclear material generates intrinsically a RN emergency in the area of transit due to the perceived hazard of radiation exposure being the material out of regulatory control (MORC) and no more in compliance with safety standards.

In RN emergencies, radiation mapping is the process to locate and identify the source(s) of radioactivity in the areas where the emergency is taken place and possibly to quantify their intensity. In the past, airborne surveys for radiation mapping in major radiological and nuclear incidents have been performed with manned aircraft, equipped with large radiation detectors with the weight of around 80kg. For instance, during the operation *Morning Light* in 1978, to respond to the crash of the Kosmos 954 nuclear powered satellite in North-West Canada, aircrafts equipped with NaI (Sodium Iodide) detectors (volume: 50350 cm³) flew at 300m above ground to map radiation and to plan radioactive debris recovery⁹.

⁸ https://www-pub.iaea.org/MTCD/Publications/PDF/PUB1830_web.pdf

⁹ Q. BrisMTOM, “The application of airborne gamma ray spectrometry in the search for radioactive debris from the Russian satellite Cosmos 954”, 1978, Geological Survey of Canada, Paper 78-1B, P.151

On the one hand, , this action provides superior results with respect to ground-based surveys for radiation mapping in terms of area coverage and safety of FR. On the other hand, the altitude at which the manned aircraft operates and the radiation detectors field of view (FOV) drastically reduce the spatial resolution of the data acquired. For instance, for a flight altitude of 150m and a detector FOV of 56° (typical of scintillators) the resolution is 239 m. This resolution may be improved by operating at a low altitude with a low-flying UAV.

It follows that, in the present context, the UAV is to be used primarily by the FRs in conjunction with competent authorities for situational awareness purposes and primarily radiation survey mapping. The operational concept is that, when a radiation emergency occurs, first responders deploy the UAV to determine the location of radiation sources, to survey the area and generate a map of radiation levels, to plan the response based on the nature of the emergency and implement that response.

The intended use of an UAV in the scene is then to:

- Support to incident response commands,
- Improve situational awareness of incident response team,
- Localize the threat in space,
- Carry on a radiological survey of the affected area.

Primary users (operators) of the UAV in this CONOPS are FRs such as fire-fighters and/or law enforcement officers. The full list of end-users of data acquired by the UAV is presented in the following table.

End-users	Short description
Fire fighters	Local emergency service personnel lacking adequate experience in the assessment of radiological hazards.
Law enforcement agencies	Local emergency service personnel lacking adequate in the assessment of radiological hazards.
Incident Commander (IC)	A single incident commander, possibly supported by a command group, responsible for directing the response of all the organizations responding to the emergency. During the early stages of a radiological emergency, this would typically be the fire chief or lead local law enforcement officer. This position may be passed to another person upon the arrival of qualified local or national officials.
First responder monitor	Individual equipped and trained to use basic radiation monitoring instruments but is not a qualified radiological assessor. He/she will only perform simple assessment tasks. In most cases, the first responder monitor will not be available immediately and must be requested from a nearby user of radioactive material (e.g., hospital, university, research reactor).
Radiation assessor	Individual trained, equipped and qualified to assess alpha, beta, neutron and gamma emitting material, perform radiation surveys and dose assessments, control contamination, ensure radiation protection of emergency workers and issue recommendations on protective actions. In most cases, this person will not be available for at least several hours to provide radiation protection support upon arrival.

Nuclear power plant emergency response team	Incident response team composed of plant personnel and civil authority personnel specifically trained to respond on site to the occurrence of an accident at a nuclear plant.
Incident enquiry personnel	Personnel assembled by the legal branch or by the Government to investigate and report on any nuclear incident. Characteristics of this group could be diverse: legal personnel, financial specialists, engineers and scientists.

End-users are most of the time the operator of the drone, i.e., an organization owning and deploying the drones in the mission area and ultimately responsible for the drones' operations. The End-User appoints a pilot, who is responsible for operational safety of the drone during all phases of the flight.

4.2. Needs of first responders

As the use of drone technology expands in multiple areas, this is also the case in the forever widening range of applications for emergency services. Drones are an excellent tool for first responders (FRs), reducing health risks and saving lives through avoiding hazardous situations, and guiding critical decision-making. Firefighters, search and rescue teams, and members of security forces can deploy tailor-made drones within minutes. FRs are using UAVs to produce 3D maps, scan for victims, and assess damaged infrastructure. If the UAV is equipped with radiation detectors, video camera and thermal imaging, this provides FRs with the ability to establish the presence of radiation and determine its levels at the same time as seeing through smoke, dust, light fog, and vegetation. Since these requirements apply to all FRs, a growing global demand for such UAVs can be foreseen.

An aerial radiation survey using a small UAV has several advantages for FRs:

- *Safety enhancement:* FRs don't have to enter potentially harmful areas of high dose rates to carry out radiation measurements; low risk of structural damage to buildings and the environment during its operation;
- *Time savings:* FRs can survey a large area in a relatively short time period, e.g., by using a drone swarm consisting of 5 drones, an area of 1 km² can be mapped in about 30 min;
- *Costs savings:* UAV deployment costs orders of magnitude less as compared to using a helicopter or winged aircraft;
- *Increased personal protection:* FRs do not have to enter the area of high risk (potential collapse of the damaged building, high level of radioactivity, fire, explosive gases, etc.), but can obtain situational awareness from a sensor-equipped UAV operating at a remote location;
- *Remote surveillance of hard-to-reach buildings and dangerous areas:* FRs can operate remotely the video- and thermal cameras and radiation detector(s) on a UAV, using video goggles in order to extend the range of operation under pilot control. Depending on the software and obstacle avoidance capability of the UAV, this can also be applied indoors.

The hazardous and complex threat situation of FRs operating in locations contaminated by radioactivity, potentially combined with explosive threats and fire, results in demanding

technical and operational specifications for *Small Unmanned Radiation Detection (URD) System*. Such a system consists of the following main components: airframe, propulsion unit, on board sensors, and remote ground control system (GSC).

All of these components have to be taken into account in selecting the optimal Small URD System with the following characteristics:

- *Airframe*: Integrated carbon frame constructed to be both light and stiff for maximum performance; umbrella-fold design for quick deployment and ease of storage; all weather UAV operational in wind gusts up to 60 km/h and ambient air temperature ranging from -5 C to +40 C; sensors and micro-controller (including battery) all enclosed within one container mounted on a universal gimbal;
- *Propulsion*: several battery-powered electric motors with rotors (quadcopter, hexacopter, octocopter), or hybrid-power (petrol-powered combustion engine/generator providing electric power for motors); top cruising speed 80 km/h, hover speed 0 km/h; brushless percussion system; operational time with the internal battery up to 45 min for an electric UAV, respectively 4 h for a hybrid UAV;
- *Sensors*: radiation detector(s) capable of measuring a dose rate, ideally ranging from 0.1 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ to 1 mSv/s; scintillator detectors NaI(Tl), CeBr₃, LaBr₃(Ce) or NaITM for gamma and neutron detection; independent spectroscopy- and dosimetry probes for gamma detection integrated in a rugged housing for outdoor environments; multiple gamma spectrometers connected to one unit, working simultaneously with a high dose level detector equipped with two energy compensated Geiger-Mueller (GM) tubes and mini air sampler for air contamination measurement (one GM tube for gamma monitoring of surroundings, second GM for detection of alpha, beta and gamma radiations emitted by aerosols captured on the electret sampling filters); gamma spectroscopy unit with spectra resolution from 256 up to 2048 channels and an energy range from 50 keV to 3 MeV; CZT based detector: energy resolution @ 662 keV (21°C operation) <2.5% FWHM (energy range 30 keV – 3.0 MeV); CsI(Tl) based detector: energy resolution @ 662 keV (21°C operation) <7.2% FWHM (energy Range 50 keV – 1.5 MeV); real-time gamma dose rate measurement based on recalculation from spectrum; accumulation time selectable by the user, starting from 1s; HD video camera; HD thermal camera; pilot video system First-Person-View (FPV); ambient air temperature; relative atmospheric humidity; barometric air pressure; embedded real-time clock providing time/date fix (GSM and GNSS); laser ranging to determine height above the surface, monitored from ~1m to over 100m;
- *Telemetry*: Remote vehicle telemetry wirelessly to pilot tablet; spread spectrum frequency hopping; dual GNSS GPS for positioning; Way Point Navigation for wide area radiological threat search; wireless communication directly to the ground control station where a GIS map visualizes trajectory and radiation measurements; onboard web interface for easy configuration of the system and isotope-based alarms; georeferenced map of the measurements for a real time data visualization; internal data storage in the main unit as well as wireless real-time data transfer to the control unit; data tagged with GPS coordinates and stored on-board for post-flight download

and viewing; transmitting data to a base station for immediate viewing; position fixing (latitude and longitude) by multi GNSS (GPS, GALILEO and GLONASS), number of satellites and height above mean sea-level (AMSL); data can be displayed as a full gamma spectrum, which allows to identify radioactive isotopes that are present; data in mapping application includes counts per second (CPS) over time; URD system using software to combine radiation intensity and geolocation data to produce high-resolution mapping of radiation levels;

- *Control unit:* Remote ground control system (GCS, “ground cockpit”) enabling flight control of UAV, visual information on the flight path and numerical information (power level, GPS data); autonomous flight pattern creating radiation maps in a distance of up to 100 km from the base of operation; all radiation- and flight data can be evaluated during the flight; UAV can be sent to an identified radiation hotspot (or highest dose rate) for a detailed measurement; autonomous and fully automatic return and landing.

4.3 Required UAVs Capabilities for Detection, Identification and Monitoring

UAVs could substitute FRs in RN emergencies by providing detection, identification and monitoring operations aimed primarily at improving personnel’s safety by addressing the ALARA (*As Low As Reasonably Achievable*) radioprotection principle. In fact, the deployment in the crisis area during a RN emergency of drones in the **subcategories A2 and A3 of Open drones' category** cannot solve the crisis but it enables the possibility to accomplish specific functions in place of human operators and minimizing their exposition to a radiation field that most of the time is unknown in the early phases of the emergency. Once that these functions are executed by the UAV, the mission of human forces in the crisis area can be successfully and safely accomplished. To this end, UAVs’ utilization must be properly planned, considering also its limitations, in order to define what kind of functions could be effectively accomplished in place of the responding teams. Such functions are specified as follows:

a. Route Identification: It focuses on obtaining information about a specified route and terrain conditions along which a RN hazard could influence the movement of human forces. This function raises awareness of route conditions from the point of view of radiological exposure levels for FRs and allows to plan interventions paths for the FRs in the area and the use of appropriate PPEs. This function is all the more relevant in the case of rescue operations in areas with limited access. The procedures associated with this function are summarized below:

- (1) Determine contaminated locations on the route.
- (2) Define contamination boundaries.
- (3) Mark clear bypass routes.
- (4) Determine protection level;
- (5) Report and mark RN hazards across the route.

b. Area Identification: This function it is aimed at confirming the presence of potential or suspected RN threats / hazards or contamination within a given area. It is associated with the

intervention of FRs in scenarios where the crisis is raised by information alert rather than an already confirmed presence of RN agents. The procedures associated with this function are:

- (1) Survey allegedly contaminated area;
- (2) Report and mark hazards in the area;
- (3) Define zones of interventions-

c. Area Monitoring: After the identification of an area with RN contamination, the UAV function is to monitor how it evolves in terms of dimension and level of contamination. This function may require specific monitoring in identified hot spots and must consider the possibility of the UAV to adapt its flight altitude to the encountered obstacles in the area.

d. Aerial Monitoring: Conducting aerial monitoring is key to evaluate if contamination is spreading from the terrain to the atmosphere and *vice versa*. This function allows to define and report on contaminated areas on the flight route. Part of this process could be related to environmental monitoring for possible health consequences on personnel and the surrounding population. This utilization could support consequence management procedures by receiving timely important information regarding atmospheric contamination in order to be used for saving lives purposes.

e. Point Monitoring: It provides intermittent or continuous observation of a specific RN-related place, such as structure, person, or object. It is related to scenarios where the RN emergency has a clear specific source that can be also a moving target (i.e., boat, car, train). This process is limited when conducted by UAVs, depending on the specific terrain conditions and its approaching abilities related to movement restrictions, such as obstacles and buildings. However, the UAV type and size could provide enough solutions on this matter, but in general it can't substitute human factor in details. To this end, it is assumed that detailed point monitoring has to be conducted by responding teams, while general monitoring could be made by UAVs.

f. Sample management: Sample collection could be conducted by UAVs with appropriate capabilities, especially when it is related to radiological emergencies. It is related to its payload capabilities to work as a collector device, beyond detection and identification ones, which depends on mission priorities and planning prerequisites. UAV sample collection can be conducted ahead of personnel one, providing timely and serious information on area radiological contamination levels, in order to plan the next steps on operations. This function is usually categorized under the "Specific" category of missions (See Sec.4.5) and may require an operational authorization, based on risks assessment produced by the drone operator.

Summarizing, UAV capabilities can play an important role in RN detection, identification and monitoring operations by substituting responding teams in several fields and therefore reducing time and human effort. To this end, UAVs function on RN detection, identification and monitoring could precede force's one in order to provide significant information for the following operational / tactical steps and prepare the right personnel's reaction in a safe and effective way.

4.4 Mission scenarios

Based on the previous analysis, it is possible to identify reference mission scenarios in RN emergencies, where drones in **subcategory A3 of Open drones' category** may address a solution to the IFAFRI capability gaps 6. Considering the approach adopted so far, the following mission scenarios are assumed as relevant for G516 and establish a reference for the development of Sec.4.2:

Mission Scenario no. 1: Sources seeking and localization

- The area to be investigated is outdoors and where reportedly it is expected to find radiation sources (gamma emitters) sealed or unsealed; examples: search for orphan sources and MORC
- The area is accessible by a small drone. In case of investigation in a wooded area, low flying drones are the only alternative to helicopters. In case of an urban area, low flying drones may navigate in streets around buildings.
- Radiation data needed: Georeferenced gamma dose rate on the ground; isotope identification.
- Result: Gamma-dose rate map with radiation hot spot detection; isotope data.

Mission Scenario no. 2: Survey of radionuclides deposited on the ground

- The area to be investigated is outdoors and contaminated by different gamma-radiation emitting radionuclides, deposited on the ground (fall-out; wash-out); example: accident in nuclear power plant, crash of a nuclear-powered satellite, aftermath of a Radiation Dispersal Device (RDD) event.
- The area is accessible by a small drone. In the case of investigation in a wooded area, low flying drones are the only alternative to helicopters. In the case of an urban area, low flying drones may navigate on streets around buildings.
- Radiation data needed: Georeferenced gamma dose rate on the ground; isotope identification;
- Results: Gamma-dose rate map with radiation hot spot detection; isotope data.

Mission Scenario no. 3; Radioactive plume tracking

- The area to be investigated is the radioactive plume in the atmosphere after a nuclear incident; example: accident in nuclear power plant
- Priority of survey in the downwind sector of the damaged nuclear site.
- Radiation data needed: Radioactive aerosol concentration in the atmosphere; isotope identification;
- Results: Gamma-dose rate map; radioactive aerosol concentration in the atmosphere (low flight can provide an alert on eventual fall out); isotope data.

Mission Scenario no. 4: On site survey in a nuclear incident

- The area to be investigated is outdoors, surrounding the collapsed/damaged reactor building in the aftermath of an explosion in a nuclear plant. Harsh operative conditions due to high radiation levels, high temperatures and presence of aggressive chemicals. OTS UAV likely not able to sustain these conditions.
- The area is accessible by a small drone and the low flying capability allows to adapt the flight to the obstacles due to rubble piles.

- Radiation data needed: Georeferenced gamma/neutron dose rate in the atmosphere; georeferenced gamma/neutron dose rate on the rubble piles; isotope identification;
- Results: Gamma/neutron-dose rate atmospheric/rubble pile map.

Mission Scenario no. 5: Internal survey in a reactor building

- The area to be investigated is the inside of a reactor building, where a radioactive leak is suspected or took place. UAVs can inspect upper floors of the building that are not accessible to UGV (i.e., stairs with high inclinations);
- The area is accessible by a small drone qualified to operate in confined spaces (collisions tolerant). Possibility to use tethered drones (permanent physical link, in the form of a flexible wire or cable, to provide power and communications to a UAV).
- Radiation data needed: Georeferenced gamma dose rate inside the building; isotope identification;
- Results: Gamma-dose rate map with radiation hot spot detection

Mission Scenario no. 6 Source search after an information alert

- The area to be investigated is a cargo container terminal in an international seaport, where an information alert has raised an alarm that a criminal organization is attempting to finalize an illicit trafficking of radiological material. The type of radionuclides is unknown as well their activity. The shielding provided by the container walls allows detection of gamma radiation only.
- The area is accessible by a small drone and its low flying capability allows to adapt the flight to the obstacles posed by stacked containers.
- Radiation data needed: Georeferenced gamma dose rate on the ground; isotope identification;
- Results: Gamma-dose rate map with radiation hot spot detection

Mission Scenario no. 7: Possible trafficking of RN material aboard containership

- Coastguard receives Information on suspected containership carrying illegal radiological material.
- The ship approaches the port for mooring and unloading cargo amounting to 50.000 tons.
- Coastguard sends its fast patrol boats to restrain ship's cruise for inspection.
- CBRNe team arrives and gets aboard to conduct detection and identification operations.
- They use a drone with a radiation detector on board for external inspection
- If this option fails, they continue by opening available containers for internal inspection by the use of a special drone with capabilities for this task (able to move among obstacles).
- If they don't detect anything, the ship is ordered to moor at port for unloading and detailed inspection of all containers
- If they locate illegal radioactive material, they follow procedures for collection of material, transportation and disposal.

Mission Scenario No8: Truck crash inside city road carrying radioactive material

- Truck crash happened due to heavy rain, resulting in its overturn and cargo movement

- Its cargo contains a container with goods containing radioactive material for industrial use.
- There is panic among the city population due to residents' identification of boxes with radiation symbols.
- Mass media spread the news making the situation worse.
- Due to unidentified radiation dispersion in the atmosphere around responsible authorities decide the use of UAVs for detection, identification and monitoring purposes, before any action is executed by first responders.

The scenarios considered are summarized in Tab.1

Tab.1 Reference mission scenarios for low-flying UAVs

Mission scenario		Short description	Outdoor/ Indoor	Expected results
#	Name			
1	Sources seeking and localization	– search for orphan sources and MORC	Outdoor	– gamma-dose rate map – radiation hot spot detection; – isotope data
2	Survey of radionuclides deposited on the ground	– survey in the downwind sector of the damaged nuclear site, – RDD – Satellite crash	Outdoor	– gamma-dose rate map – radiation hot spot detection; – radioactive aerosol concentration in the atmosphere; – isotope data
3	Radioactive plume tracking	– after a nuclear incident; – survey in the downwind sector of the damaged nuclear site, – long in time,	Outdoor	– gamma-dose rate map; – radioactive aerosol concentration in the atmosphere; – isotope data
4	Outdoor survey of the collapsed/damaged reactor building in the aftermath of an explosion in a nuclear plant	– characterized by high radiation levels, high temperatures and presence of aggressive chemicals; – difficulties in wireless communication above the operations area, – requirements of high-quality real-time surveillance,	Outdoor	– gamma/neutrons-dose rate, – atmospheric / rubbles map
5	Possible reactor leak	– characterized by small spaces (corridors and rooms), – difficult access to GPS or wireless communications inside,	Indoor	– gamma-dose rate map – radiation hot spot detection

6	Source search after an information alert Radiation source search in cargo terminal	– illicit trafficking of radiological material in cargo containers, operation in the international seaport cargo terminal, the type of radionuclides is unknown, detection only of gamma radiation possible	Outdoor	– gamma-dose rate map – radiation hot spot detection
7	Possible trafficking of RN material aboard containership	– illicit trafficking of radiological material in cargo containers, inspection of the containership,	Indoor & Outdoor	– radiation hot spot detection
8	Truck crash inside city road carrying radioactive material	– Urban space limited by buildings around,	Outdoor	– gamma-dose rate map – radiation hot spot detection

4.5. UAV categorization and requirements for G516

The international UAV market is large and offers a multiplicity of drone models, ranging from handheld micro-drones with a Maximum Take Off Mass (MTOM) below 250g¹⁰, to aircraft-size drones with a MTOM of 4 650 kg.¹¹ The GAP 516 narrows the interest to *low flying UAVs with payload high enough to carry out radiation measurements*. The following sections present the actual categorization in force in the EU for drones and how it can be used to precisely determine the perimeter of interest of this study.

RN-related Drone Selection

A large number of different drone models have been developed in recent years. The global drone market is structured on the basis of:

- (1) *Type*, i.e., as Fixed-wing, Rotary Blade, and Hybrid;
- (2) *Application*, i.e., Filming & Photography; Inspection & Maintenance.

The wide range of drone models available internationally necessitates a clear categorization. In the European Union, EU Regulations 2019/947 and 2019/945 set out the framework for the safe operation of civil drones in the European skies. They adopt a risk-based approach, and what they consider is the weight and the specifications of the civil drone and the operation it is intended to conduct. Regulation (EU) 2019/947, which is applicable since 31 December 2020 in all EU Member States, including Norway and Liechtenstein (it is expected that it will soon become applicable in Switzerland and Iceland too), caters for most types of civil drone

¹⁰DJI *MINI*, length below 20 cm; <https://www.dji.com/at/mavic-mini/specs> (last visited 19 January 2021).

¹¹ Israel Aerospace Industries (IAI) *Eitan*. It has a wingspan of 26 m and a length of 13 m, powered by a 895 kW turbojet engine; Largest operational unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) | Guinness World Records; (last visited 19 January 2021).

operations and their levels of risk. It defines three categories of civil drone operations: the ‘open’, the ‘specific’ and the ‘certified’ category.

- The ‘open’ category addresses the lower-risk civil drone operations in, where safety is ensured, provided the civil drone operator complies with the relevant requirements for its intended operation. This category is subdivided into three subcategories, namely A1, A2 and A3. Operational risks in the ‘open’ category are considered low and, therefore, no operational authorization is required before starting a flight.
- The ‘specific’ category covers riskier civil drone operations, where safety is ensured by the drone operator by obtaining an operational authorization from the national competent authority before starting the operation. To obtain the operational authorization, the drone operator is required to conduct a risk assessment, which will determine the requirements necessary for the safe operation of the civil drone(s).
- In the ‘certified’ category, the safety risk is considerably high; therefore, the certification of the drone operator and its drone, as well as the licensing of the remote pilot(s), is always required to ensure safety.

The ‘open’ category is in turn subdivided in three sub-categories, A1, A2 and A3 and based on the MTOM (Maximum Take Off Mass) that are further broken-down into Classes:

- A1: MTOM<900g.
- A2: 900g<MTOM<4Kg.
- A3: 4Kg<MTOM<25Kg.

Additional operational restrictions apply to each class of drone, in particular with regard to the distance that must be maintained between the drone and non-involved persons. Figure 1 provides a summary of the operations authorized in the open category for each class of drones.

UAS		Operation			Operator/pilot	
Class	MTOM	Subcategory	Operational restrictions	Distance from people	Operator Registration Required	Remote pilot competence
Privately built	< 250 g	A1	*Operate in visual line of sight below 120 m altitude *Fly away from airports *Respect specific rules defined by the zone in which you operate	You can fly over uninvolved people (not over crowds)	No	Read owner manual
C0						<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Read owner manual •Perform online training •Pass online test
C1	< 900 g	A2		You can fly at a safe distance from uninvolved people	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Read owner manual •Perform online training •Pass online test •Pass a theoretical test in a centre recognised by the aviation authority (only if you intend to fly close to non involved people)
C2	< 4 kg		A3	You should: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fly in an area where it is reasonably expected that no uninvolved people will be endangered • Keep a safety distance from urban areas 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Read owner manual • Perform online training • Pass an online test
C3	< 25 kg					
C4 (model aircraft)						
Privately built	< 25 kg					

Figure 1: Operations authorized in the open category for each class of drones as defined by EASA opinion 01/2018

All drones in the “Open” category must be remotely piloted within a Visual Line Of Sight (VLOS) and at a maximum height of 120m range (Fig. 10) and no operational authorization is required before starting a flight.

Figure 2: Limitations for piloting a drone within Visual Line of Sight (VLOS)

In Open category an autonomous flight is not allowed while an automatic flight it is permitted. In an autonomous flight the pilot has no way to interfere with the drone which executes the mission by itself. In an automatic flight the drone path is pre-programmed by the pilot, who retains the possibility at any time to recover full manual control of the drone. In addition, in Open category is not allowed for the drone to carry dangerous goods and to drop material. Looking at the “Operational restrictions” column of Fig. 1, it is clear that they are met in all the reference scenarios of Sec.4.3.5. Taking into consideration the VLOS constraint, this restricts scenarios 3,4 and 5 to low INES scale incidents, presumably up to INES 4.

For reasons of limited practicality in handling them (MTOM exceeding 25Kg) and costs, drones in the “Specific” and “Certified” categories are in the present framework considered as unsuited for EU first responders involved in RN-related operations. Also, such drones must be operated after having acquired the necessary authorization. This is contrasting with the First Responders necessity to deploy the resources quickly. Moreover, within the “Open” category A1 subcategory has a limited payload capacity, making it unsuitable for carrying even medium-sized radiation detectors as payload.

A2 subcategory (900g<MTOM<4kg) and A3 subcategory of “Open” category (2Kg<MTOM<25 kg) provides first responders with platforms of high utility at relatively low cost. The small physical size, ease of assembly and employment, and relatively low cost are attributes that make them prime candidates for use in an RN-related operation.

Therefore, in this document for “small low flying UAVs” are meant drones in the A2 and A3 subcategories of the Open drones’ category as in the EU Regulations 2019/947 and 2019/945.

Looking at the “Operational restrictions” column of Fig. 9, it is evident that they are deployable in all the reference scenarios of Sec.4.3.5. without breaching the EASA rules. The situation is different, if one takes into consideration the VLOS constraint. This restricts scenarios 3,4 and 5 to low INES scale incidents, presumably up to INES 4, like for instance the onsite response plan in low power nuclear premises, such as research reactors.

RN Mission Critical Issues

For the most part, no launch system or dedicated geographical area is required for the employment of Open category UAV. The wide range and capability of aerial platforms in this category enable a first responder organization to tailor the platform, guidance and propulsion system, payload, sensors, and the desired effects to be achieved to the specific mission. Nevertheless, First Responders involved in an RN-related mission need to perform complex tasks under harsh operating conditions, and drones should provide reliable support in their work with a payload of up to several kilograms. Currently, drones in this category can support RN-related missions in many ways, as already pointed out in Sec.4.2 and Sec.4.3, such as:

- Enhanced situational awareness in the disaster area;
- Airborne warning of hazardous situations;
- Environmental monitoring;
- Comprehensive aerial photography added to radiation mapping;
- Remote sensing;
- Large scale monitoring of disaster recovery;
- Aerial surveillance in hazardous areas over extended periods;
- Meteorological data for different altitudes above ground level (AGL);
- Traffic monitoring of evacuation operations.

Each mission has a set of variables that must be achieved by the drone. Most drones are rather specialized, i.e., they meet the requirements for only a few of the above missions. This can necessitate the deployment of several types of drones in a disaster area.

Drone Structural Design

A drone airframe-design for application by FRs in an RN-related mission must meet the following criteria:

- Low drone weight to enable flight duration exceeding 15 min;
- Fast drone assembly at deployment site;
- Easy drone launch and recovery;
- High degree of maneuverability;
- Capability to carry a wide range of different radiation detector systems on-board;
- Capability of reaching adequate operating altitude (minimum 25 m AGL);
- Sustaining harsh operating environment (i.e. strong wind, dust, high temperatures, mechanical stress);
- Adequate range (minimum 2 km);
- High degree of structural stability;
- End-user friendly handling, transport, storage and maintenance.

Drone Airframe

An important aspect of drone selection is the construction method and material used to build the airframe. Up-scale drones use composite materials, combining low specific-weight with high mechanical sturdiness. This requires advanced composite manufacturing technology,

e.g., working with glass fibers or, better still, graphite fibers.¹² These novel construction techniques increase drone capabilities and decrease manufacturing costs. An RN mission can expose a drone to high levels of mechanical stress. Therefore, a drone airframe made of a composite material is advantageous over a, e.g., PVC-based drone.

Drone Propulsion

The choice of drone propulsion system is also among the important drone selection criteria for an RN mission. The technical options cover jet, propeller, rotary, tilt rotor and fan. Besides the cost factor, the energy source required by a certain propulsion technique determines ultimately the choice. For rapid drone deployment at a reasonable cost, as well as low maintenance costs, multiple electric motors are considered optimal to provide propulsion. It is important for an RN-related deployment of drones to take into account – besides the drone energy consumption for propulsion - also the energy needs of the on-board radiation sensors used during the mission, which may necessitate auxiliary energy sources. This is particularly the case for long missions lasting several hours. In this case tethered versions of power supply may be a viable solution.

Drone Operations

Drones require a *Mission Planning System (MPS)*. MPS provides complex functions in support to the drone operator, during the preparation of assigned RN-related operations (pre-flight study of mission feasibility; mission debrief with post-flight mission analysis after mission accomplishment in order to assess the results; share lesson learned). An MPS allows FRs to plan a route with minimum time and risk, supporting them during all phases of planning activities: from receiving the order, up to pre-flight briefing and preparation of on-board materials. Obviously, a flight route planned inside a built-up city is more complex than outside a city, where there are fewer tall buildings, communications towers and power lines.

In selecting the drone launch site, the time of flight and anticipated weather conditions are of importance. Long flight times increase the probability of navigation errors. Heavy rain or high winds can preclude the launch of a drone. The requirement for launching a drone during daylight or at night will directly impact the type of platform guidance. A short-range daytime launch would enable line-of-sight control of the platform by a tablet or small computer. Another option is the flying of pre-programmed waypoints using GPS. This guidance option would also be applicable for drone night operations.

Care must be taken to ensure the drone control and data link frequencies, if required, will not be jammed by normal communication transmissions in the launch area, enroute to the target or in the target area itself.

Upon reaching the reserve capacities of the battery packs, the drone will automatically switch to homing mode, i.e., returning to the base station without the help of the ground-based operator- Alternatively, the MPS can induce a soft emergency landing operation, if the homing mode is no longer possible to achieve.

Small drones for the most part require almost no logistics support base. As the platforms are small, they can be easily dis-assembled, transported to the launch site and re-assembled using hand-held tools.

¹² In a composite material, the fiber carries majority of the load, and is the major contributor in the material properties. The resin transfers the load between fibers, prevents the fibers from buckling, and binds the materials together. The carbon-carbon chain has extremely strong molecular bonds.

The most demanding phases of using a drone in an RN-related mission are launch and recovery. During these two operational phases there is an increased probability of drones being damaged. For the most part, no launch system or dedicated geographical area is required for the employment of the drone. Besides the safety for the drone itself, it is even more important that during these two phases RN personnel and bystanders involved are safe. A common launch method is take-off from a flat area in preferably open space. Recovery is usually carried out in the same such area, preferably without any major obstacles (trees, electric power- or telephone lines) nearby.

An overview of standardized operations is outline in *ISO 21384-3 Unmanned aircraft systems - Part 3: Operational procedures*

Drone-Sensor-Ground Cockpit Communication

Drones used in RN-related missions can either operate under manual control (requiring a trained and licensed drone pilot) from a ground station under constant visual control by the pilot, or autonomously. In either case, adequate communication is key in order to avoid collision (e.g., with buildings), to ensure a safe return of the drone in hazardous situations (e.g., running out of power) and to transmit data (e.g., video, radiation measurements) in a secure manner. Such a communication link can be provided by a mobile ground station or satellite. In any case, emphasis has to be placed on reliable communications under all operational conditions during the RN-related mission.

In case of complex RN-related missions deploying advanced tools, such as multiple radiation detectors on-board of the drone flying between buildings, the pilot needs an assistant to operate the tool, enabling the pilot to focus on the flight operations. The communication should also be fault tolerant and resistant to interference.

RN-related operations can involve security sensitive information. In this case it is important to encrypt drone-based communication to prevent hijacking or interception of data.

Drone Control

Every type of drone deployed in an RN-related operation has a control system, encompassing hardware and software installed on the drone and at the control station, such as processors, memory devices, data busses, sensors and input/output devices. These control systems detect errors or fault conditions and take appropriate action, e.g., in case of loss of communication between drone and control station, the drone will return to a pre-selected position to resume communications, or to land autonomously.

A control system used for an RN-related mission must be compatible with the potentially harsh mission operating conditions, such as: increased acceleration; excessive vibration; multiple radio frequency interference; high degree of atmospheric humidity; extreme ambient atmospheric temperature; high wind speeds; powerful wind gusts.

Data Management

Frequently, drone missions require dealing with large amounts of data. Furthermore, data management needs to address various stages: Data acquisition; data processing; data storage; data transmission.

Some drones transmit data in real-time to ground stations. In this case bandwidth can be an issue and various compression methods may be used to deal with large amounts of data.

Other drones must store data on-board until recovery (e.g., 3D photogrammetry for creating terrain models). This requires robust data storage devices.

Upon receipt of the data, it is usually processed further for subsequent use (geo-referenced mapping; corrected for distortions; screening for errors).

Onboard Drone Sensors

Sensors are an important part of many drone designs. Usually, the airframe is designed to allow the mounting of several sensors. The following sensors are considered as minimum equipment for an RN mission:

- (1) Flight sensors to monitor flight variables;
- (2) Sensors to monitor mission-specific variables (radiation type; isotope; dose rate; relative atmospheric humidity; ambient air temperature; barometric pressure);
- (3) HD video camera;
- (4) HD thermal camera;
- (5) HD photo camera with zoom.

Video- and thermal cameras are attached to a remotely controlled flexor, enabling the operator to change the camera-angle within a range of 90°. The horizontal angle can also be adjusted. All onboard sensors are connected to the onboard *data storage-management system* to generate GPS-supported datasets of the relevant sensor input for either immediate or later use. Visualization of the data is done graphically on display units in order to facilitate fast recognition of hazard-threshold levels (e.g., radiation dose limit). Thereby, the system provides the crisis manager with a visual presentation of video/photo images (VIS), supplemented with infrared (IR)-images, in addition to the measurement data.

Digital output signals are fed into the *data-processing unit* aboard the drone. The software installed on the on-board PC handles the incoming video stream as a live feed or as snapshots in pre-selected time intervals via a downlink transponder to the ground-based operator. The onboard-storage medium enables recording of the continuous flow of video- and thermal camera image data for later use, and at the same time acts as a flight-recording system by storing flight-relevant parameters along with the GPS-coordinates onto the drive.

Drone Storage and Transport

During storage of electrically powered drones LiPo batteries require constant maintenance by using special battery chargers. The optimum battery charge is between 30% and 90% capacity.

Depending on the type of drone, the storage space required can be significant (typically 0.5 m² for a drone with foldable arms; about 1 m² for a drone with detachable arms). Drones for deployment in an RN-related operation need to be transported from the storage area to their operating location. In order to protect electronics and sensors from damage during transport ruggedized, tailor-made drone- and sensor transport containers have proven useful.

Drone Selection Criteria

In order to determine what drone and features are required for application in an RN-related operation, the following topic areas need to be addressed:

1. *What environment will the drone be used in?*
 - Take-Off Altitude

- Temperature range
- Humidity range, wind speed and gusts
- Obstacles (forests, mountains, buildings, power lines)
- Disturbances (Radio towers, GSM antennas, Wi-Fi)
- Access before Take-Off

2. *What are specific requirements concerning the drone?*

- Operating Altitude (AGL)
- Distance from pilot
- Flight time
- Automatic flight mode features
- Number of axis for gimbal
- Single or dual operator

3. *What payload is needed?*

- Weight
- Dimensions
- Power supply of payload
- Data links needed with the drone.

4.6. International survey of suitable COTS UAVs

According to IAEA's guidance¹³ after Fukushima's nuclear accident (2011) a methodology had been developed and tested for UAVs equipped with radiation detectors, cameras and GPS devices for use in routine or emergency conditions. These UAVs can synchronize radiation readings and other information with their exact GPS position for receiving specific radiation dispersion / measurements in the most effective way.

To fulfill the task of effective monitoring, an UAV must be equipped with several components to detect, identify, and possibly quantify the contamination occurred. Moreover, to confirm the assessment of the substances involved in the release, it is preferable to foresee a sampling system for different kinds of substances.

To this end, an international survey was conducted to identify suitable COTS UAVs, which can be accordingly adapted for radiation monitoring by proper sensor installation.

This section provides an overview of generic UAV requirements for carrying a radiation detector, and several examples of COTS available UAVs.

4.6.1 UAV Requirements

UAVs (drones) are available in three configurations:

- *Copter*: Reflecting the number of engines, copters are available in the configuration as quadcopter, hexacopter, and octocopter; copters with a TOW of several kilograms are a popular platform for mounting radiation sensors;

¹³<https://www.iaea.org/newscenter/news/now-available-new-drone-technology-for-radiological-monitoring-in-emergency-situations>

- *Vertical take-off and landing (VTOL) drone*: Mostly designed for commercial or military-use in inspection- and surveillance missions;
- *Helicopter*: Helicopter drones differ from other drones because they only have two rotors instead of four, six or eight. They are more challenging to manoeuvre than copters and VTOL drones.

Since GAP 516 focuses on “small” UAVs, the generally larger and heavier COTS VTOL and helicopters are not included in this document.

Within the framework of the INCLUDING project a UAV needs to fulfil the following monitoring-, surveillance-, and survey tasks: (1) Detecting radioactive material trafficked illegally (e.g., being hidden in cargo); (2) Mapping an area contaminated with different radioisotopes (e.g., due to an uncontrolled radioactive release); (3) Detecting a radiation source misused as radiation exposure device (RED). In order to fulfil these tasks, a UAV - designed for carrying a radiation detection system - should meet one or more of the requirements listed below.

Airframe

The UAV platform should be able to fly in fully autonomous and/or manual mode, or both. Thereby, the easily manoeuvrable UAV is able to fulfil the same tasks as a manned helicopter but with significantly lower maintenance requirements and overall costs. Provided the airframe is made of suitable material (carbon fibre, aeronautical grade aluminium), the light weight of the UAV enhances its versatility in carrying out different missions. If the take-off weight (MTOM) is below 25 kg, such a drone will not be affected by stricter EU regulations associated with a higher MTOM class, otherwise severely limiting the deployment of a heavier UAVs. Also, low MTOM increases the endurance of the UAV.

Power Supply

Small COTS UAVs are mostly powered by electric engines, which are either connected to pre-charged batteries or to an on-board alternator/generator, driven by a petrol-powered combustion engine (typically small 2-stroke engine). Batteries have the advantage of being simpler in their electro-mechanical design. An on-board alternator offers a longer range (typically 2.5 hours endurance and a range up to 30 km with 3 kg payload). It is advantageous for the UAV to have a redundant power supply on-board for increased operational safety (additional batteries), e.g., an alternator provides redundancy to the system, and in the event of generator failure, the backup battery takes over. All on board electronics should be rated IP64 or higher.

Payload

UAV payload capacity depends on the type of power supply (batteries or petrol tank), as well as the weight of the airframe and batteries, respectively petrol-driven generator. Figure 3 shows the typical relationship between flight time (in minutes) and payload (in kg) for two different battery configurations for a COTS drone.^[1]

Optimally, the UAV should be able to carry on-board: Radiation detector; day light sensor with continuous optical zoom; night vision sensor with uncooled infrared; laser pointer; gyro-stabilized, geo-referenced electro-optical/infrared (EO/IR) sensor; three-dimensional micro-mechanical inertial measurement unit (IMU); radio relay; transponder.

Figure 3: Example of the relationship between UAV payload and UAV flight time for a hexacopter drone (MTOM: 15.5 kg; wheelbase: 1.1 m)

Flight Controls and On-board Electronics

The UAV control unit covers a wide range of tasks: Auto take-off and landing; Auto Flight plan execution (waypoints); Hover and Fly-to; Auto Return-To-Base (RTB) in case of communication failure; Manual override, Camera/radiation detector (payload) stabilization, pointing and control. The camera, autopilot and the engine monitor are interconnected, providing the operator with important information onscreen in real time. This includes inter alia remaining battery capacity/fuel quantity, flight plan, telemetry, payload details and video. Autopilot is integrated with sensors, including high precision GPS antenna, proximity sensor, and rpms sensor.

Electronic systems are protected in several ways: (a) Electrical systems are individually isolated from vibrations; (b) Main wiring uses MIL-SPEC connectors; (c) Wiring is protected against abrasion, vibration and corrosion; (d) Payload and servos power supply ports are protected by resettable fuses, ensuring that the remaining systems will continue working in the event of a subsystem failure.

Documentation

Operation of a UAV, equipped with a radiation detector, requires comprehensive documentation on the UAV, pilot and the mission, such as: Radiation detector functionality (detector calibration, radiation background reading), Pilot operation handbook, UAV platform logbook, Pre-flight checklists, and Maintenance manual. The documentation needs to be written to aeronautic standards.

4.6.2 COTS UAV Overview

The table below provides examples of COTS UAVs which are potentially suitable as platform for mounting a radiation detector. They vary with regard to the physical size (wingspan, wheelbase) of the UAV, Take-off Weight (MTOM) and payload; the latter is decisive for the flight time of the UAV. As a general feature, these drones are designed to carry different sensors (e.g., camera) on board, i.e., they can be modified to carry radiation sensors as well.

Tab.2 Overview of COTS UAV

UAV Model	Supplier/Country	UAV Type/Make	Wheel base (mm)	Max. Take-off Weight, kg	Max. Payload, kg	Flight Time	Comments
GAIA 100	FoxTech, P.R.China	Hexacopter	1035	6.6	3	50 min	High flight performance and better loading capacity for aerial filming and photography
F1000 Pro	FoxTech, P.R.China	Quadcopter	1065		3	60 min	Long flight time quadcopter
THEA 140 Hybrid Pro	FoxTech, P.R.China	Quadcopter	1400	8.8	5 (excluding 1.6L gasoline)	6 h with no payload; 4.5 h with 2 kg payload	Quadcopter for industrial application, upgraded with a new 2000W generator Halo-2000
RiCOP TER	Riegl, Austria	Octocopter	1920 (wingspan)	25	6.5	30 min with maximum load	High performance X-8 array foldable surveying octocopter. Provides full mechanical and electrical integration of sensor system (including radiation sensors) components into aircraft fuselage
UAVS Ghost 60	UAV Solutions Inc., USA	Quadcopter			2.5	20 min (56 min with 435 g payload)	Tactical multi-rotor design intended for missions requiring long endurance, highly-capable payloads, and secure communications
HYBRiX 2.1	Quaternium, Spain	Octocopter	1249	25	10	2 h (full load)	Multirotor hybrid drone that provides up to 4 hours of operational flight time with only 25 kg MMTOM
AD-F	Actiondrone, USA	Quadcopter	1470	9	3	45 min	AD-F is a multi-purpose aerial platform, compact and lightweight design. Payloads can be configured for mapping, surveying, inspection work, etc.

Hercules 10	Dronevolt, France	Octocopter	900	20	7.5	35 (15 min with maximum load)	Light, compact and extremely resistant drone for a wide range of payloads
EVO4H SE	Italdron SRL, Italy	Quadcopter	630	9	2.5	30 (15 min with maximum load)	Powerful, stable and reliable drone
SKYLL E 1550	MMC UAV, P.R.China	Hexacopter	1550	21	10	75	Fire-proof, rain-proof and dust-proof carbon fiber one-body fuselage; 20 km communication; 10 km video transmission
Notuzi B90	MMC UAV, P.R.China	Quadcopter	920	9	3	48	5 km HD video transmission
Notuzi X85	MMC UAV, P.R.China	Quadcopter	850	9	3	50	Small, fast and intelligent drone for a wide range of applications
ATYGES FV6	Atyges, Spain	Hexacopter			1	30	Industrial drone for aerial photography, inspection, civil defense, topography
ATYGES FV8	Atyges, Spain	Hexacopter			1	30	Industrial drone for aerial photography, inspection
MATRICE 200	DJI, P.R.China	Quadcopter	887 (wingspan)	6.14	1.61 to 2.34	24 (max. payload/TB55)	Robust design with boarding capacity of multiple cameras
MATRICE 300 RTK	DJI, P.R.China	Quadcopter	895 (wingspan)	9	2.7	31 (max. payload)	Robust and intelligent industrial drone
MATRICE 600 Pro	DJI, P.R.China	Quadcopter	1668/1133	15.5	5.5	18 (max. payload), 38 (no load)	Robust and intelligent industrial drone with 5 km data transmission
UAV Quadcopter V650	Aretas Aerial, Canada/USA	Quadcopter	650			30	Multi-functional, yet powerful, platform for a variety of COTS sensors. Sensor readings can be transmitted wirelessly up to 40 km from an irradiated hot zone and viewed through the online Reporting,

							Mapping and Analytics system
UAV Hexacopter V680	Aretas Aerial, Canada/USA	Hexacopter	680			Variable depending on sensor load	Industrial quality, stable, mid-size UAV. Specialized mounts allow for effective placement for gimballed HD cameras and multiple on-board sensors
UAV Octocopter V1000	Aretas Aerial, Canada/USA	Octocopter	1000			Variable depending on sensor load	The large octocopter platform has the capacity for a large sensor payload while maintaining reliability and redundancy. One can connect via live satellite link and gather sensor data from anywhere in the world

Of interest is the solution proposed by Flyability¹⁴, a Swiss company, building safe drones for inaccessible places (Figure 4). By allowing drones to be used safely inside cities, buildings, and in contact with people, it enables new interactions and services with UAVs and solves the two most critical issues of one of the fastest growing industries: collision and injury risks. The company's main market is in industrial inspection where it avoids sending people in dangerous and confined spaces for the inspection of Power Generation, Oil & Gas or Maritime infrastructures. It is also active in Search & Rescue and Security to assess emergency situations without putting humans at risk. ELIOS is a collision-tolerant drone, designed for the inspection and exploration of the most inaccessible places. Allowing for the first time to fly in complex, cluttered or indoor spaces, It unleashes the potential of UAVs in numerous applications where their use was previously too dangerous or simply impossible.

¹⁴ <https://www.flyability.com/elios/>

Figure 4: Collision-resistant drone ELIOS.

Aerialtronics¹⁵

Aerialtronics designs, produces and services commercial unmanned aircraft systems. Their latest generation, the Altura Zenith, combines state of the art technology with a flat, compact, and lightweight design (Figure 5). With a wide range of payload compatibility, from dual vision cameras to gas sniffers to radiation detectors, Aerialtronics’ systems can be applied to a wide variety of segments including: Safety & Security, Inspection, Surveying & Mapping, Agriculture, and Research. Altura Zenith drone has flexibility so that any payload of 3 Kg can be adapted to fit the Altura Cardan payload connection, including radiation sensors / detectors.

Figure 5: Altura Zenith ATX8 drone.

4.7. Radiation measurement systems

4.7.1 Detectors types

The types of ionizing radiations that may be involved in a RN emergency are photons, like x and gamma rays, and particles, like alpha, beta and neutrons. Their detection is based on the interaction mechanisms with matter. Alpha and beta particles have an electric charge and interact with matter through Coulomb interaction and cause ionization directly. Conversely, neutrons and photons do not bear any electric charge and ionize the material with which they interact indirectly by transferring their energy to charged particles. The table below reports the different categories, types and characteristics of radiation detectors.

Table 2 Radiation detectors

Category	Type	General constituents	Principle	Characteristics
Gas-filled detectors	Ionization chambers	A metallic cylinder filled with a gas at atmospheric pressure (Air or Ar for alpha, beta and gamma detection,	Gas molecules get ionized when energetic charged particles propagate through the gas (primary ionization).	Widely used in hand held radiation survey meters to measure beta and gamma radiation. In some adaptations also neutrons

¹⁵ <https://www.aerialtronics.com/en/products/altura-zenith#fit>

		<p>BF₃ for neutrons detection) and with two isolated flat electrodes at which is applied a voltage difference typically 100-200V.</p>	<p>The voltage is not high enough to produce further ionization in the gas (secondary ionization).</p> <p>The signal is proportional to the primary ionization that is in turn proportional to energy of the ionizing particle (spectroscopy).</p> <p>For neutrons detection the incoming neutrons produce alpha particles when they react with the boron atoms in the detector gas.</p>	<p>No dead time. This is due to the fact, there is no inherent amplification of signal in the operating medium and therefore these types of counters do not require much time to recover from large currents.</p> <p>They are particularly preferred for high dose rate measurements and for gamma radiation they give good accuracy for energies above 50-100 keV.</p>
Proportional counters	<p>A cylindrical tube (cathode) containing a mixture of methane (90%) and argon (10%), a fine tungsten wire along the axis of the tube (anode).</p> <p>Typically, voltage difference in the range of 300-600V.</p>	<p>Gas molecules get ionized when energetic charged particles propagate through the gas. The ions so produced (primary ionization) get accelerated by the high voltage difference between electrodes and cause further ionization in the gas (secondary ionization).</p> <p>The signal is proportional to the primary + secondary ionization.</p>	<p>Ability to measure the energy of incident radiation, by producing a detector output pulse that is <i>proportional</i> to the radiation energy absorbed by the detector due to an ionizing event.</p> <p>It is used where energy levels of incident radiation must be known (spectroscopy), such as in the discrimination between alpha and beta particles, or accurate measurement of X and gamma rays radiation dose.</p>	
Geiger Muller counters	<p>A hollow cylindrical tube (GM tube, cathode) of length about 10-15cm and filled with a gas mixture (generally Ar with 10% vapours of ethyl alcohol) at a low pressure of about 0.1 atmosphere. A tungsten wire (anode) is fixed along the axis of the GM tube.</p> <p>The potential difference between</p>	<p>The electrons generated by the ionization process are accelerated and cause ionization of more gas molecules generating within a very short interval of time (avalanche) that give rise a high current pulse. Same signal generated independently of the incident ionizing energy.</p> <p>It is not common, but Geiger counters may be also used for neutron detection. In this case, Geiger-</p>	<p>Robust and inexpensive detector.</p> <p>Unable to measure high radiation rates efficiently (cannot operate above about 10⁴ counts per second).</p> <p>Cannot measure incident radiation energy.</p> <p>No spectral information can be generated.</p> <p>No discrimination between radiation types; such as between alpha and beta particles unless specific entrance windows are mounted on the detector.</p> <p>Two windows type:</p>	

		<p>the two electrodes is >600V.</p>	<p>Mueller tube must have the inside of the tube coated with boron, or the tube must contain boron trifluoride (BF₃) or helium-3 as the fill gas.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Glass: no alpha detection - Mica: Possible alpha detection <p>No neutrons detection unless the inside of the tube is coated with boron, or the tube contains boron trifluoride or helium-3 as the fill gas. The neutrons interact with the boron nuclei, producing alpha particles, or directly with the helium-3 nuclei producing hydrogen and tritium ions and electrons. These charged particles then trigger the normal avalanche process.</p>
<p>Solid state detectors</p>	<p>Semiconductors</p>	<p>They are composed of two layers of a semiconductor material, one "n-type," which means it contains a greater number of electrons compared to holes, and one "p-type," meaning it has a greater number of holes than electrons. Electrons from the n-type migrate across the junction between the two layers to fill the holes in the p-type, creating what's called a depletion zone.</p>	<p>Ionizing radiation interacting with the atoms inside the depletion zone causes them to re-ionize, and create an electronic pulse which can be measured.</p>	<p>HP Ge detectors are based on pure crystals of Germanium</p> <p>In Ge(Li) detectors Lithium ions compensate for impure Germanium crystals.</p> <p>HPGe and Ge (Li) detectors must be operated at liquid nitrogen temperatures to eliminate thermally generated electrons from the conduction band.</p> <p>HPGe and Ge(Li) allows for high resolution gamma ray spectrometry.</p> <p>The disadvantage is that germanium detectors are much more expensive than ionization chambers or scintillation counters.</p> <p>CZT (Cadmium-Zinc-Telluride) detectors operate at room temperature and allow for reduced dimension and high energy resolution (spectrometry)</p>

	<p>Scintillation chamber</p>	<p>Scintillation detectors work through the connection of a scintillator material with a photomultiplier (PM) tube.</p> <p>The PM tube uses a photocathode material to convert each pulse of light into an electron, and then amplifies that signal significantly in order to generate a voltage pulse that can then be read and interpreted.</p>	<p>A scintillator material generates photons in response to incident radiation</p> <p>The light created in the scintillator strikes the photocathode of a photomultiplier tube, releasing at most one photoelectron per photon.</p> <p>Suitable for alpha, beta and gamma radiation detection and in some adaptations also for thermal neutron detection.</p>	<p>The most widely used scintillation material are NaI(Tl) (thallium-doped sodium iodide), CsI(Tl), LaBr3(Ce) and Bismuth Germanate (BGO),</p> <p>Lil(Eu) is a scintillator mostly used for thermal neutron detection.</p> <p>The advantages of a scintillation chamber are its efficiency and the high precision and counting rates that are possible.</p> <p>The intensity of the light flashes is proportional to the energy of the radiation, so, these counters are suited to measure the energy of gamma radiation (gamma spectroscopy) and, therefore, can be used to identify gamma emitting isotopes.</p>
<p>Liquid detectors</p>	<p>Liquid Scintillators</p>	<p>Liquid scintillators detectors work through the connection of a liquid solution with a photomultiplier (PM) tube.</p> <p>The PM tube uses a photocathode material to convert each pulse of light into an electron, and then amplifies that signal significantly in order to generate a voltage pulse that can then be read and interpreted.</p>	<p>The liquid scintillator is made of a solution where the solvent is an organic aromatic liquid and the solute are fluorescent molecules.</p>	

Whatever the radiation detector type, for operation onboard a UAV it must meet the following basic requirements:

1. High efficiency
2. Selectivity
3. Low weight;
4. Small size;
5. Low power requirements;
6. Operation without cooling.

Radiation detector efficiency is given by the ratio of the number of particles of radiation detected to the total number of particles of radiation emitted. The required efficiency of a radiation detector to be installed on a UAV depends on the mission to accomplish and hence on the scenarios listed in Sec.4.1.

Geiger Muller (GM) basically fail to meet requirements 1 and 2. In fact, GM tubes cannot differentiate which type of radiation is being detected, cannot be used to determine the exact energy of the detected radiation (no selectivity) they do not require cooling. They are useful to FRs for making an initial determination of radiation risk and are a good choice for radioactive plumes tracking.

Scintillators have been so far the first choice for radiation detectors to install on a UAV. They are selective and allow radionuclides identification.

4.7.2. Radiation Detector Requirements

Radiation detectors suitable for mounting on a UAV should meet one or more of the requirements detailed below.

Radiation detection:

Detection of radiation can be carried out without the need for discrimination between different isotopes, e.g., deploying an energy compensated Geiger-Müller detector. In case radionuclide identification is needed, either low resolution gamma-ray spectroscopy (e.g., using a NaI(Tl) detector), or high-resolution gamma-ray spectrometers are available (e.g., self-contained CTZ detector with built in preamplifier, shaping amplifier, baseline restorer, pulse height digitizer, and high voltage supply). High spectral quality enables accurate threat identification and classification even in mixed source environments. High-end detectors are available with high spatial resolution and high detection sensitivity, localizing gamma-ray emitters even at low energies. Commonly, radiation detectors allow the determination of both, dose rate and count rate. Selected detector systems compensate for natural radiation background (e.g., deploying peak shape adaption). Also, acquired data can be locally assigned using an integrated GPS receiver (*location tagging*).

Data Evaluation:

Dedicated software can differentiate between radiation originating from naturally occurring radioactive materials (NORM), medical- and industrial radioactive materials, as well as special nuclear materials (SNM). Estimation of the dose rate at the measurement point in real time is available for a wide range of source strengths (up to 1 Sv/h). In case of an uncontrolled release of radiation, two alarm levels for both dose and dose rate are considered useful, as well as an indication of possible accumulated dose inaccuracy due to overload.

Data Management:

State-of-the-art (SOTA) radiation detectors can be equipped with a wireless network interface to transfer data to a "base station" computer. Stored data files can be sent to third party experts for reach back and adjudication. The radiation detector can be integrated into a customized network platform where alarm(s), dose, and isotope ID are provided as an output by the detector. This will allow the use of a single control point for multiple integrated sensors. Increasingly, radiation detectors have access to a library of radionuclides.

Physical parameters:

The payload on a drone has a major impact on the available flight time of the drone, i.e., a light-weight radiation detector is an inherent advantage. Lithium Polymer (LiPo) batteries with high energy density are SOTA technology. Since they offer greater power and runtime than older NiMh batteries, they are the preferred electric power source for drones. However, air-travel restrictions apply for LiPo batteries, potentially limiting their use in international operations.

A dual battery management system enables uninterrupted operation in challenging situations, i.e., internal rechargeable battery and replaceable batteries are used either by themselves or together. In either case, long battery life (operation for several hours per battery pack) is crucial.

Radiation detectors mounted on drones are likely to be exposed to harsh weather conditions (heavy rainfall, snow). Therefore, ruggedization of the detector is essential, enabling operation in high or low temperatures. The radiation detector mounted on a drone needs to have a drop-proof housing, be waterproof and dustproof (e.g., IP65 capable). Since the operational environment of the radiation detector may be heavily contaminated, detector housing needs to withstand full decontamination procedures.

4.7.3 COTS Radiation Detector Overview

This section provides an overview of examples of radiation detectors, which are suitable as drone payload, provided the detector weight is in compliance with the maximum take-off weight (MTOM) as defined by the drone manufacturer. Adaptation work is likely to be necessary to adapt a specific COTS detector for mounting on a drone, unless a ready-made detector-drone system is acquired. COTS radiation detectors cover a wide range in terms of detector type, system weight and system size. In addition, the software installed has an equally wide range of capabilities. Figure 6 depicts the decisions to be made in selecting the optimal radiation detector for the task as offered by a supplier.

Figure 6: Decision-tree for selecting the optimal radiation detector for mounting on a drone

Figure 7 shows a typical example of a radiation detector which can be mounted onto drones, assuming some adaptation to detector housing and electronics has been made in order to fit as payload.

Figure 7: Micro-Radioisotope Identifier (ORTEC, USA)

Table 3 provides an overview of some radiation detectors, which are in principle suitable for mounting onto a drone. The actual match between detector and drone has to account for the detector characteristics and defined operation.

Table 3: Overview of COTS radiation detectors in principle suitable for mounting onto a drone (adaptive measures necessary).

Model Description	Manufacturer	Detector	Capability	Size/Weight	Comments
D230A UAV Gamma Ray Spectrometer	Terraplus, CA	Up to four 1204cm ³ Bismuth Germanate (BGO) or Sodium Iodide (NaI) detectors	Gamma	51 x 51 mm BGO: 2.5 kg (1) to 7 kg (4 detectors) NaI: 2.1 kg (1) to 5.4 kg (4 detectors)	Real-time transmission of data, including spectra, dose rate, elevation, atmospheric pressure, and GPS position. The D230A also records data onto an internal 32 GB SD card with a standard storage capacity of 40,000 full spectra samples.
PoCAMon - Personal Alpha/Beta Continuous Air Monitor (CAM)	SARAD, DE	400mm ² ion-implanted silicon detector	Alpha/Beta	Suitable for wearing by a person	Standard NiMH battery pack 12V/3.8Ah. Achieves an operation time of more than 30 hours
NucScout - Doserate Meter and Nuclide Identifier	SARAD, DE	NaI(Tl) with integrated photo multiplier and high voltage supply	Gamma	270mm x 195cm x 210mm / 2.5kg	Up to 28 user selectable nuclides. Operation: min. 8 hours (14h typ.). NiMH battery with internal charger or wall adapter (18V)

RadEye SPRD-ER Personal Radiation Detector	Thermo Scientific, UK		Gamma and X-rays plus neutrons via prompt gamma	104 x 66 x 41 mm / 195 g (incl. batteries)	2 x AAA alkaline or NiMH. Battery life > 170 h (alkaline)
RadEye GN Gamma Neutron Pager	Thermo Scientific, UK	Li-6	Gamma and Neutron	96 x 31 x 61 mm / 160g	Battery life > 300 h
RIIDEye S/M Handheld Radioisotope Identifiers	Thermo Scientific, UK	Gamma detector Options: (1) 2 in. x 2 in. NaI Scintillator, (2) 1.5 in. x 1.5 in. LaBr offered in both models, (3) 3 in. x 3 in NaI	Gamma	32 x 25 x 15 cm / 2.3kg	Standard rechargeable (8hr nominal) and adapter. Audio through speaker and visual on screen
PackEye Radiation Detection Backpack	Thermo Scientific, UK		Gamma and neutron (Gamma only available)	58 x 30 x 18 cm / 6kg	Rechargeable NiMH, power pack (7.2V). 30 h (20h with PDA operation via Bluetooth)
Detective X Ultra High Resolution HPGe Radioisotope Identification Device	ORTEC, USA	P-type HPGe crystal with Coaxial construction; lithium-6 fluoride/zinc sulfate (Li6F/ZnS) detector	Gamma and neutron	39.5 x 16 x 21cm / 6.8kg (gamma only); 7.7kg (gamma/neutron).	2 Rechargeable Lithium Ion batteries, 98 Wh each, nominal. Approximately 8 hours of battery life at 25°C when HPGe detector is cold. <4 hour time to charge.
Micro-Detective-HX Advanced Handheld Radiation Detection and Identification RIID	ORTEC, USA	P-type HPGe crystal with Coaxial construction	Gamma and neutron	37.4 x 14.6 x 27.9cm / 7.25kg	Lithium Ion. 14.4 V, 6.2 Ah, 89 Wh, nominal. Up to 5 hours of battery life at 25°C when HPGe detector is cold. <4 hour time to charge
Micro-Detective Ultra-light, Portable Hand Held Radioisotope Identifier	ORTEC, USA	P-type HPGe crystal with Coaxial construction	Gamma and neutron	37.4 x 14.6 x 27.9cm / 6.9kg	Lithium Ion. 14.4 V, 6.2 Ah, 89 Wh, nominal. Up to 5 hours of battery life at 25°C when HPGe detector is cold. <4 hour time to charge. Battery lifetime may be extended indefinitely by the use of external battery packs
Detective-100T HPGe-based Hand-Held Radioisotope Identifier	ORTEC, USA	P-type HPGe crystal with Coaxial construction	Gamma and neutron	39.4 x 18.3 x 34.9 cm / 12kg	>3 hours at 25°C when HPGe detector is cold. Battery lifetime may be extended indefinitely by the use of external battery packs which

					are available in "battery belt" formats.
RayMon10 hand-held rugged isotope detector	Kromek, UK	CZT-solid state	Gamma		Long-life rechargeable battery – 8 hours continuous
GR1 Gamma-Ray Spectrometer	Kromek, UK	CZT based detector	Gamma	10 x 10 x 10 mm	Energy resolution @ 662 keV (21°C operation) <2.5% FWHM. Energy Range 30 keV – 3.0 MeV. Can be connected to one unit, including battery, and work simultaneously within one container mounted on a universal gimbal
SIGMA 50 radiation detector	Kromek, UK	CsI(Tl) scintillation	Gamma	Crystal size: 25.4 x 25.4 x 25.4 mm; Case size: 35x35x130 mm, 300 g	Energy resolution @ 662 keV (21°C operation) <7.2% FWHM. Energy Range 50 keV – 1.5 MeV. Can be connected to one unit, including battery, and work simultaneously within one container mounted on a universal gimbal. Gamma spectroscopy and mapping software: 10Hz snapshot rate of units data providing high resolution at speed, count per second (CPS) and spectral data transmitted simultaneously every 1 second. Data in mapping application includes CPS over time; energy spectrum; CPS and location; dose estimation; isotope characterisation.
D3S ID wearable RIID gamma neutron detector	Kromek, UK		Gamma and neutron	<0.5 kg	One of the fastest and most accurate isotope ID devices on the market, that operates in both high dose and low dose radiation environments.

						Identifies 22 more isotopes than RIID standard: ANSI N42.34. Four times faster than RIID standard. A fraction of the size and a fraction of the cost of other RIIDs
D5 RIID wearable gamma neutron detector	Kromek, UK	CLLBC detector	Gamma and neutron	<1 kg		Small, light, 3.5% resolution wearable RIID with an expansive radioisotope library and an ultra-low false alarm rate. It continuously scans and accurately identifies radiological threats in real time, even in mixed source environments
IPIX™ Ultra Portable Gamma-Ray Imaging System	Mirion Technologies, USA	CZT based detector/Pixelized CdTe detector	Gamma	2.5 kg (with batteries)		Performance linear up to 10 Sv/h (1000 R/h). Battery life – up to 4 hours per replaceable batteries
AreaRAE Pro Portable Multi-Threat Detector	RAE Systems by Honeywell, USA		Gamma	6.5 kg		Battery run time 12-20 hours
Tracerco Personal Electronic Dosimeter (PED) ER	Tracerco, UK		Gamma	10 x 6 x 2 cm / 160 g		Bluetooth transmission to an Android device, GPS tracking

4.8. International survey of suitable COTS radiation detection UAVs

The international UAV market is extremely dynamic and is predicted to grow by US\$ 3.3 Billion by 2024 worldwide.¹⁶ The factors expected to fuel the growth of the drone market include *inter alia* the increasing use of drones for security- and safety services. The drone market is segmented among major players, such as: China, U.S., Russia, Germany, United Kingdom, France, Italy, Israel, Japan, Switzerland, and others. Whilst companies in these countries develop many UAV models in competitive rivalry for general use (capable of delivering mostly videos, photos, thermal images, meteorological data, radargrams¹⁷), some companies have

¹⁶ Market Research Engine, "Drone Market Size By Type (Fixed-wing, Rotary Blade, Hybrid), By Application (Filming & Photography, Inspection & Maintenance), By Region (North America, Europe, Asia-Pacific, Rest of the World), Market Analysis Report, Forecast 2018-2024." <https://www.marketresearchengine.com/drone-market> (last visited 19 January 2021).

¹⁷ Data from ground penetrating radar.

already identified a niche in the radiological survey sector and integrated radiation sensors on board of a UAV. This section provides an overview of examples of these special COTS UAVs with a ready-to-use radiation measurement system on board.¹⁸ The list has not the ambition to be exhaustive due to the ever-growing launch on the market of new solutions but only indicative of the efforts of producers and industrial players to meet the FRs needs. The list includes also some advanced developments from research projects.

GAMON Drone

GAMON Drone is a compact radionuclides identification system designed for wide area radiological threat search (Figure 8). GAMON Drone includes independent spectroscopy and dosimetry probes for gamma detection, integrated in a rugged housing for outdoor environments. It provides wireless communication directly to the ground control station (GCS). A GIS map visualizes trajectory and measurements without affecting the UAV/UGV connections and performances.¹⁹

The drone has on-board scintillator detectors NaI(Tl), CeBr₃, LaBr₃(Ce) or NaI^L™ for gamma and neutron detection. The onboard web interface allows configuration of the system and isotope-based alarms. Results are displayed in a georeferenced map of the measurements as real time data visualization. Further details are summarized in the *Appendix* (drone no. 1).

Figure 8: GAMON Drone

NuEM Drone G

The NuEM Drone G from NUVIATECH is co-axial quadcopter, designed for environmental radiation monitoring (Figure 9). It is suitable of surveying smaller areas to search for uncontrolled radioactive sources, potential contamination or work in places with hazardous dose level. This RMD module consists of a NaI(Tl) gamma spectroscopy probe (optionally 2x2 inches or 3x3 inches), a high dose level detector equipped with two energy compensated GM tubes, and a small air sampler.

¹⁸ Any mentioning of hardware or software does not represent any recommendation for purchasing this equipment. DWARE OR SOFTWARE DOES NOT REPRESENT A RECOMMENDATION FOR PURCHASING THIS EQUIPMENT

¹⁹ <https://www.caen.it/products/gamon-drone/> (last visited 19 January 2021).

Figure 9: NuEM Drone G

Time and position data are synchronized with GPS. Real-time gamma dose rate measurement is based on recalculation from the spectrum. Accumulation time is selectable by the user starting from 1sec. The module offers internal data storage in the main unit as well as a wireless real-time data transfer to the GCS.²⁰ Further details are summarized in the *Appendix* (drone no.2).

Zoe

The Zoe is an all-weather quadcopter, which can fly a variety of nuclear detection sensors and provide real time data acquisition (Figure 10). Detailed aerial inspections can be provided for a variety of different sites, including nuclear power plants and associated stacks and roofs.²¹ Further details are summarized in the *Appendix* (drone no.3).

Figure 10: Zoe

²⁰ UAV radiation monitoring and survey - NUVIATech Instruments (nuviatech-instruments.com)_(last visited 26 January 2021)

²¹ <https://www.flycamuav.com/aerial-radiation-detection/>_(last visited 26 January 2021)

NEO

The NEO drone is an all-weather, co-axial X8 octocopter using a carbon frame (Figure 11). It is specially designed to fly in rain and wind gusts up to 55 km/h. All of the electronics are integrated inside the carbon frame and are sufficiently cooled allowing for operations in a hot climate.²² Further details are summarized in the *Appendix* (drone no. 4).

Figure 11: NEO Drone

RadKnight Baron Drone

The UAV *RadKnight Baron* by RADeCo Inc. may utilize various radiation detection payloads (Figure 12).²³

Figure 12: RadKnight Baron Drone

The hexacopter configuration with an integrated carbon frame provides an adequate lift for light to medium loads. Umbrella-fold design allows for quick deployment. The UAV is able to transfer live time radiological data to the *Q Ground Control*. In addition, the UAV has a built-in live video downlink and a thermal camera. Further details are summarized in the *Appendix* (drone no. 5).

²² <https://www.flycamuav.com/aerial-radiation-detection/> (last visited 26 January 2021)

²³ <https://radecoinc.com/product-details/radknight-baron/> (last visited 26 January 2021)

Mirion Javelin

The Mirion Javelin by RAdCo Inc. is a vertical takeoff and landing (VTOL) vehicle with an operation range of 70 km (Figure 13). The system is specifically designed for Emergency Preparedness applications.

Figure 13: Mirion Javelin Drone

The Javelin is can carry a variety of payloads, including Mirion radiological detection equipment, such as the SPIR-Explorer, RDS-31 and Telepole II. In addition to the FPV-pilot view video, the Javelin can be outfitted with high definition-infrared and zoom video systems.²⁴ Further details are summarized in the *Appendix* (drone no. 6).

Kromek UAV Radiation Mapping Drone

The radiation mapping drone is designed as a low-altitude aerial radiation detection UAV (Figure 14). The system provides real-time location, measurement and mapping of radioactivity with isotope identification.²⁵ The drone has the following sensors: positioning fixing (latitude and longitude) by multi GNSS (GPS and GLONASS), number of satellites and height above mean sea level (AMSL); ambient air temperature, ambient relative humidity and barometric pressure; embedded real-time clock providing time/date fix (GSM and GNSS available as back up); laser ranging to determine height above the surface.

²⁴ <https://radecoinc.com/product-details/javelin/>(last visited 26 January 2021)

²⁵ <https://www.kromek.com/product/aerial-radiation-mapping-drone/>(last visited 26 January 2021)

Figure 14: Kromek UAV Radiation Mapping Drone

Sensors and micro-controller, including battery, all enclosed within one container mounted on a universal gimbal. The drone incorporates an autonomous airborne radiation monitoring system (AARM). AARM provides low altitude-mapping of radioactive contamination and delivers meter-resolution maps of radiation, including over high dose areas and inaccessible locations. AARM is comprised of ImiTec's Remote Isotopic Analysis System TM (RIASTM) mounted on a small UAV system (SUAS). The payload contains a lightweight Kromek gamma spectrometer and positioning devices, utilising software to combine radiation intensity and geolocation data to produce high-resolution mapping of radiation levels and identification of isotopes present. Multiple gamma spectrometers can be connected to one unit and work simultaneously. 10Hz snapshot rate of data provides high resolution at speed, count per second (CPS) and spectral data transmitted simultaneously every second.

E-DRAD (Enea Drone RADiometer)

ENEA, as a part of several activities funded by European projects has developed a system composed by a commercial drone, DJI Inspire 2²⁶ equipped onboard with a Geiger Muller detector for radiation survey mission. The system is shown in Figure 15.

²⁶ www.dji.com/uk/inspire-2/info#specs

Figure 15: E-DRAD (Enea Drone RADiometer)

The radiation sensor is a Geiger Muller counter which can record radioactive decays with energies in the range 70 keV-2 MeV. It has a length of 111mm and a radius of 11mm, the operating voltage is 350V and saturates a 30000cps.

The GM counter is located inside a box made with a 3D printer that hosts also a Raspberry OS for the control and transmission of the data to the ground station through a radio channel at 868MHz. Data acquisition can be manual or automatic. In manual mode the operator decides when acquire the data that are real time transmitted. In automatic mode, data are acquired every 12 s but stored on the Raspberry and not transmitted. Data acquired can be real time visualized on a GIS map to produce georeferenced radiation maps. The drone can operate in automatic flight mode.

UAV md4-1000 by Scientific and Industrial Centrum “ASPECT” (Dubna, Russia)

ASPECT (Russia) developed in 2013 a radiation survey device on the base of unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) as an equipment of rescue forces for radiation situation reconnaissance in case of emergency (Figure 16). The device is multi range radiometer with spectrometer functions capable to work within gamma ray fields of dose rate 10^{-7} – 10^{-1} Sievert per hour. UAV md4-1000 (Microdrones GmbH, Germany) was selected as the carrier as a reliable vehicle with appropriate properties. The device mounts a spectrometer on the base of NaJ(Tl) crystal and two Geiger-Muller counters as radiation sensors. Spectrometric measurements are used within the dose rate range from 10^{-7} Sv/h to 10^{-4} Sv/h, Geiger-Muller counters cover the dose rate range 10^{-4} - 10^{-1} Sv/h.

Figure 16: Drone ASPECT md4-1000

The main characteristics of the system are:

Payload mass limitation	1,2 kg
Energy range	0,05 – 3 MeV
Relative energy resolution at 662 keV (137Cs)	7,5%
Calibration stability for 8 h operation	±1%
Maximal spectral count rate	$1,5 \cdot 10^5 \text{s}^{-1}$
Number of spectrum channels	230
Dose rate measurable	from 10^{-7} to 10^{-1} Sv/h
Scintillation detector sensitivity (for Cs-137).	$430 \text{ s}^{-1}/\mu\text{Sv}$

TEKEVER AR3 system

The AR3 Net Ray is a small UAS with long endurance (up to 10 hours), specially designed for maritime and coastal surveillance missions, but also supporting different types of land-based operations (Figure 17). Due to its communications range of up to 80 Km, as well as its reduced logistics footprint (short set-up time and easily installable launch and recovery system), the AR3 platform meets all the requirements to support medium- to long range operations. In fact, this platform is launched using a highly mobile catapult system and can be recovered by parachute and airbags (standard recovery option for land-based operations), or with a net system (specifically designed for maritime operations), making it extremely easy to assemble, operate and store. It can be operated on altitudes below 150m (500ft).

Figure 17: TEKEVER AR3 aircraft on the catapult

AR3 UAV general specifications	Value [units]
Dimensions (wingspan x length)	3.4 x 1.7 [m]
Maximum Take-off Mass (MTOW)	21.7 [kg]
Standard empty weight	16.7 [kg]
Maximum payload capacity	5.0 [kg]
Absolute ceiling	4500 [m]
Maximum endurance	10 [h] (mission dependent)
Maximum communications range (data link)	80 [Km]
Cruise speed	100 [Km/h]
Maximum speed	110 [Km/h]

The AR3 system is composed of the aircraft (UAV), Ground Control Station (GCS), communications system – data link and tracker, launch system – pneumatic catapult, recovery system – parachute and airbags or recovery net, universal charger, transport cases and payloads (Figure 18). Customized payloads are EO HD camera providing high-resolution optical images and/or video streams with 30x ZOOM and IR camera that typically provides a sensitive detection of humans, metallic objects, fire outbreaks and other targets or incidents on land or at sea, even in dense environments. The flexibility of the system and space available on-board makes it possible to integrate other payloads such as radiation detectors.

Figure 18: TEKEVER AR3 aircraft on the catapult

5. Lessons learned from INCLUDING Joint Actions

In the INCLUDING project, Joint Actions are activities carried out at selected testbeds made available by project partners to test innovative solutions in RN emergency scenarios and with the primary scope to share resources and knowledge. Joint Actions are designed, planned and executed to test in real settings, and with the use of live agents under the control of appointed authorities, innovative technologies and assess the best way to integrate them into existing procedures and response plans. At the moment of release of this study, three JAs have been carried out in Athens (GR), Mikkeli (FI) and Saclay (FR). In all of them drones in the Open category and equipped with radiometric sensors have been deployed. The following lessons learnt are reported from each JA for this specific aspect and of relevance for G516.

5.1 Commercial Piraeus Port of Athens Joint Action (22 Jun 2021)

The Athens JA consisted of a multidisciplinary field exercise, counteracting an attempt to smuggle radioactive sources from a port. During the exercise UAV / UGV technology was used extensively. It was a full-scale exercise designed to establish a learning environment for participants to be trained in emergency response plans, policies and procedures in such kind of crisis.

The exercise location was in Piraeus commercial port (Piraeus Port Container Terminal) to reach the most realistic JA conduct by simulating real conditions (Figure 19). The area was selected in accordance with the following scenario concept: a cargo container at port containing two ^{137}Cs orphan sources made available by the Greek Atomic Energy Commission.

Figure 19: JA Piraeus Port

The scope of this exercise required the establishment of an incident scene and responders in the field to perform those actions usually associated with an initial response to detect a radioactive source. These actions included command and control, communications, hazard identification, site security, monitoring and control of contamination and device recovery and packaging.

The different phases of the scenario and **only with details relevant for this study** are summarised hereinafter:

Phase 1: Crisis development

The event that initiated the exercise is the routine inspection by an appointed worker, from a port commercial terminal operator, of the content of a cargo container that officially, according to the transportation document, should not contain any dangerous goods. During the inspection, the worker identifies a suspicious material and with a label indicating a package containing radioactive material

The technician was curious about the material trying to examine it, resulting in dropping the source to the ground with possible radiation dispersion. He called again the police informing about the damage to the source. The duty officer told him to leave the source on the ground, move away from the spot and stay around the area to be checked by the medical element, for possible internal contamination.

It is the result of an initial assessment that the information alert is credible and that the relevant competent authorities should implement procedures and protocols with the view to interdict and interrupt a potentially criminal act, or unauthorized act, with radiological security implications.

Phase 2: Crisis Management

The General Secretariat for Civil Protection (GSCP - responsible authority for crisis management) decides that the situation justifies the implementation of any available detection measures to verify the presence of radioactive material on the suspected cargo (containers), including aerial radiological survey.

Using civil-military cooperation framework, GSCP requested Armed Forces support on meeting the threat. The Joint CBRN Coy of the Hellenic Army arrives on the incident scene and put in place all the measures to conduct an initial assessment (size up) of the scale and dimension of the crisis (Figure 20). Among other actions, Joint CBRN Coy deploys a UAVs equipped with a Geiger-Muller counter onboard to assess the irradiation level at 2m of distance from the orphan sources. The data acquired are transmitted to the Command Post, where the Incident Commander can take decisions on the next actions.

Phase 3: Consequence Management

Based on the data acquired, the Incident Commander orchestrates the interventions of the First Responders teams. All individuals involved are wearing appropriate Personal Protective Equipment. The interventions are aimed at recovering the two sources and putting them in the chain of custody.

Further actions are focused on decontamination of the area and return to normal commercial operations in the port.

Figure 20: Phases of Crisis Development and Management

The UAV deployed during Phase 2 of the crisis was a quadcopter operated by the Hellenic Air Force (Figure 21) with a Geiger Muller gamma probe on board (Figure 30) delivered by CEA (France).

Figure 21: Drone with Geiger Muller radiation detector on board

The system assembly was equipped with a Raspberry PI module for remote automation and wireless transmission of the radiation data and other key mission parameters (GPS position, height, battery status) to the Command Post. All these pieces of information were consumed by the INCLUDING Web based platform and visualized in the Incident Commander Pc. In the tables below (Tab.4) are reported the characteristics of the UAV and of sensors mounted onboard (Tab.5).

Tab.4 E-DRAD characteristics

UAV Name	Matrice 210	
Size and dimensions	Length: 887mm Width: 880mm Height: 378 mm	
Weight	Without battery: 2,800 Kg With battery (two TB55batt): 4,750Kg	
Payload	Max 1,570gr	
Autonomy	Hover: 38 min Cruise: 24 min	
Data storage	32 GB onboard	
Operating Frequency	2,400-2,483 5,725-5,825 GHz	GHz
Access point ability	Wi-Fi access point for 10 simultaneous users	
Operating environment	Temperature: -20° to 45° C Operational for day and night light conditions Use indoor and outdoor	
Sensors	a. GPS GNSS b. Dual IMU c. Barometer d. RC IO co-processors e. RSSI	
First-Person View (FPV) Camera	Zenmuse X4S/X5S/X7/XT/XT2/Z30 resolution 608*448	

Tab.5 Radiometer characteristics

Name	Smart Gamma Probe	
Type	Gamma & X-Rays	
Detector	Energy Compensated Geiger-Müller	
Displayed units	$\mu\text{Sv/h}$, $\mu\text{Sv H}^*(10)$ ambient gamma dose equivalent rate	
Gamma Dose Rate Measurement (Equivalent 137Cs)	Low Dose Rate	High Dose Rate
	0.1 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ to 100 mSv/h	0.1 mSv/h to 10 Sv/h
Power supply	Powered by USB, RS485 (and Modbus), Ethernet (PoE): no battery in probe Powered by internal battery for Wireless	
Size and dimensions	USB: 89 mm x 32 mm RS485: 96 mm x 32 mm Wireless: 108 mm x 32 mm Ethernet: 123 mm x 32 mm	
Weight	RS485 and USB: < 80 gr, without cable Ethernet < 100 gr, without cable	
Operating environment	5 °C to 40°C	

The UAV was operated in VLOS modality and never exceeded the 50m of altitude during the manual flight. In Figure 22 and Figure 23 the phases are shown during which the UAV is approaching the container with the two orphan sources inside. The pilot was able to nearly enter in the container and the data acquired revealed an activity (in count per second) that is coherent with the expectations based on the known sources characteristic as given by the GAEC. The UAV inspected also the area around the container to verify that non contamination was present in the atmosphere. The UAV mission allowed to ascertain that the radiation levels measured, above the natural background value, was solely generated by sources irradiation and with no contamination in the aerosol.

Figure 22: The drone approaching freight containers

Figure 23: The drone at freight container door

Considerations

The Athens JA of INCLUDING was a very relevant opportunity to test how current technology can address G516 in a realistic setting. "Realistic setting" is defined as the operation in an area, where the prerequisite for a radiological incident can really happen, and be conducted with real radiological sources. The UAV in the Athens JA was deployed in a scenario categorized as n°6 as in Sec.4.3.5. The low flying capacity of the drone was exploited to inspect the entrance of the cargo container while the possibility to fly up to 50m of altitude was used to measure the eventual occurrence of contamination in the air. Data were transmitted in real-time to the Command Post through a 4G/WiFi connection and were used by the Incident Commander to have an initial seize-up of the crisis and to plan commensurate actions.

The GM counter was not able to identify the types of radionuclides contained in the two sealed sources and it has been necessary to deploy in a successive phase a UGV with an onboard energy spectrometer.

The use of the drone in the JA has been one of the subjects of discussion during the evaluation phase conducted by the project partners under the lead of experts from the Nuclear Security Centre of Excellence.

It was agreed by participants to this evaluation activity that:

- a. Deploying drones with radiometric sensors onboard in a realistic environment increases training opportunities for involved personnel, aiming to enhance their operational capabilities.
- b. Collaboration among operating authorities and the team operating the drone contributes to the effective and successful accomplishment of countering a RN incident.
- c. Interoperability of drones' technologies among civilian and military responding teams is the key factor for the success of operations.

- d. Use of drone technology can effectively support operating procedures, especially for detection, identification and reconnaissance purposes, increasing personnel safety as well as teams' capabilities.
- e. Use of appropriate software for receiving, transforming and utilising all collected data by the drone plays a key role on the success and fulfilment of operations.
- f. Proper knowledge of national and international regulations on drones' operations is key to support foreign and national teams operating and collaborating for successful accomplishment of their mission.

5.2 Mikkeli Joint Action (15 September 2021)

The Karkialampi military base of Mikkeli (FI) hosted on 15th September 2021 was the second Joint Action of the INCLUDING project. It was a Field Technical Exercise (FTX), organized by the South Savo Fire Department (SSAV), with an incident scenario involving four stolen and missing orphan sources, namely Caesium-137. Various civilians were exposed accidentally to one of the radiation sources, while the remaining three sources were recovered in the nearby area after search missions. Several local authorities and military forces have been involved in the management of the crisis. The four sealed ¹³⁷Cs sources were made available by the Finnish Radiation and Nuclear Safety Authority (STUK).

The Mikkeli FTX was designed to activate the provincial/regional current capabilities to respond to a small-scale radiological incident and identify areas for improvements in procedures and to pave the way for the adoption of new technologies.

In Figure 24 an aerial map of the Karkialampi area is shown, where the FTX took place, together with the locations of the four sources. The alarm was raised by a group of youngsters, who found an unknown object in a wooden area with a sign of radioactivity danger (fake source). The discovery was linked with a malevolent act that happened two days before when four radiological sources for industrial use were stolen in the north of the Country during a civil transport.

Of the remaining three sources, two (first and second source in red) were found close to fake source by a radiometric team equipped with hand held detectors. The third source was supposed to be dislocated somewhere in a very large open-air area (300x100m, Karkialampi shooting range) without woods but with vegetation. The Incident Commander decided to deploy a drone equipped with a GM sensor onboard to survey the area and search for the eventual presence of this source.

Figure 24: Karkialampi area with the location of the 4 radiation sources used in the JA Mikkelä

The deployed system was E-DRAD from ENEA (see Sec.4.6) and it is shown in Figure 25 ready to start for the search mission in the Karkialampi shooting range and in Figure 26 during the mission flight.

Figure 25: ENEA drone with radiation detector ready for take-off

Figure 26: ENEA drone on mission

The main challenge for the mission was to adopt a searching strategy with a flight plan that maximizes the probability to find the source within the 30min. of drone batteries autonomy. Instead of the commonly adopted *zig-zag* searching trajectory, the ENEA team decided to test the *snail* like path. Figure 27 shows the aerial view of the Karkialampi shooting range, the drone take-off point and where also the drone pilot post was located, together with the snail-like flight plan for the search. The drone remained for 20s in a fixed position at a height of 10m in each one of the 20 points indicated on the map.

Figure 27: Data acquired during drone aerial survey mission

The data acquired are shown in Figure 28 without the measurement units. Two isocurves of measured radiation intensity were identified and the search further refined, showing the highest value in the centre. In the center of this isocurves a refined search resulted in abnormal zero intensity measurement in the GM. This was attributed to GM saturation due to the nearly perpendicular position of the drone with respect to the source. This assumption was confirmed by increasing the flight altitude of the drone and observing that the GM provided measurements in line with the expected trend from the isocurves.

Figure 28: Drone-measurement based map used for locating the radiation source

The source location (GPS coordinate), identified with the drone, was communicated to the Incident Commander, who sent the STUK operator to recover the source (Figure 37). The drone has been effective in accomplishing its task and achieved this within the time limits as defined by the charge capacity of the drone batteries. The source was localized within a range of GPS coordinates that were sufficiently accurate for the STUK recovery team to find it quite easily on the ground. The snail-like path search has proven effective for the rapid identification of the source.

Considerations

Especially in low-density populated and large areas, like Karkialampi, UAVs with R/N detection capability demonstrated to provide actionable results for source searching operations. The activity conducted in Mikkeli corresponds with scenario mission n°1 as in Sec.4.3.5.

UAV saves manpower, time and provides additional graphical situation awareness to field Commanders via on-line video link. In addition, use of the UAV increases work safety of the operators on the field.

However, like any other advanced technology systems, deployment of UAV systems needs to be trained constantly. The best results are to be achieved via regular training sessions in life-

like situations, such as actual devices, real terrain, actual R/N sources with various scenarios/tasks. It is difficult for simulators to provide realistic circumstances like wind, limited visibility, communication breaks, stress and general distraction which need to be trained too. The actual training is required also due to the complexity of the UAV systems. Another point of view is that training should be conducted only by actual devices. All actions and procedures should be performed automatically and with the routine matter in a real hazardous situation. Various training scenarios help staff to prepare tactics and themselves for low probability situations too.

In the JA Mikkeli, training sessions prior to the exercise proved to be very successful and provided smooth processing during the actual exercise. All devices and communication were thoroughly checked and tested prior the JA, thereby assuring flawless UAV operation performance during the FTX Mikkeli.

6. Conclusions

Filling GAP 516 represents a challenge for hardware developers, since the technical solution should provide ideally a *small* UAV with *long* UAV flight times for extended missions with a sophisticated radiation detector on board of the UAV; the latter usually resulting in a heavy payload. Therefore, the end-user needs to define first of all the radiation measurement task (type of area to be surveyed, level of radiation activity/dose rate anticipated, minimum detector sensitivity required, need for isotope identification, detector system weight, power requirements). Altogether 23 UAVs, 19 radiation detectors and 11 UAVs with integrated radiation detection systems were evaluated in this analysis.

The international survey of the *radiation detector* market carried out showed that it is well developed and can meet all requirements for assessing the level of radioactivity for a given area, terrain type, and level of contamination. Typically, the more sophisticated a radiation detection system, the higher the detector system weight, corresponding to a shorter UAV flight time for a UAV-mounted detection system. It is noted that mounting a radiation detector on a UAV may require extensive mechatronic input (gimbal, power supply, data management).

The international *small UAV* market is large and dynamic, offering a wide range of small UAVs. However, only a limited number of small UAVs is potentially suitable for carrying a radiation detection system as payload. The battery capacity of these electrically powered UAVs²⁷ determines - apart from meteorological conditions during the flight mission - the operational flight time of the UAV. Therefore, the end-user needs to define the minimum capabilities of the radiation detector for a particular radiation assessment mission in order to ensure minimum MTOM for the UAV.

The international market for *small UAVs with integrated radiation detection systems* is limited, but quickly growing. Due to the relatively small batteries on board, they are suitable for missions lasting up to 30 minutes. Furthermore, the radiation-specific capabilities of the COTS systems are limited as compared to some of the high-end radiation detectors available.

In conclusion, end-users have the choice to:

²⁷ Only battery powered UAVs are considered, since other UAV types (petrol-powered hybrid drone; VTOL) do not meet the GAP 516 requirement of *small* UAVs.

(a) Combine a COTS radiation detector with a small COTS UAV, provided they have access to a suitable mechatronic solution for the drone-detector system;

or

(b) Acquire a COTS UAV-radiation detector system with the inherent potential limitation of the integrated detector and relatively short flight missions.

Whatever the approach, it is essential to intensify the test of the solutions in close to real situations and prioritize scenarios with difficult environmental conditions to assess the limits of system performances. This includes low and high temperatures, strong wind, rain, snow, fog and uneven heights. From the point of view of the radiation sources, it is recommended to test different isotopes starting from the most representative of scenarios as in Tab.1 (^{60}Co , ^{137}Cs above all) and with unidirectional and isotropic emission. Finally, it is necessary to improve the accuracy and speed of searching algorithms for complete the mission task within the planned duration of the flight as imposed by batteries lifetime.

INCLUDING T3.2

RN/TEC GAPS

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